

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

D6.1.4: Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication plan

Lead Author: Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO)

Grant Agreement No.	101093026		
Project Acronym	EFRA		
Project Title	Extreme Food Risk Analytics		
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05		
Project Start Date	January 1 st , 2023	Project End Date	December 31 st , 2025
Project URL	efraproject.eu		
Work Package	WP6 Generating Impact		
WP Lead Beneficiary	RAINNO (RAIN)		
Deliverable type ¹ Dissemination level ²	R PU		
Contractual due date (D6.1.4)	December 31 st , 2024	Actual submission date	February 25 th , 2026
Lead Author (s)	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO)		
Contributors	Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO), Anna Romanova (SGS), Alessio Bosca (JAKALA), Franko Maria Nardini (CNR), Aron Henriksson (SU).		
Internal reviewer(s)	Charalampos Thanopoulos (AGROKNOW) & Marina Georga (AGROKNOW)		

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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	27/11/2025	10	Table of Contents	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO)
V0.2	01/12/2025	25	Initial Deliverable Structure	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO)
V0.3	08/12/2025	50	Chapters 1 - 6	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO)
V0.4	08/01/2026	70	Summary, Chapters 7 – 8, Annexes	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO)
V0.5	13/01/2026	80	Partners Contribution	Anna Romanova (SGS), Alessio Bosca (JAKALA), Franko Maria Nardini (CNR), Aron Henriksson (SU)
V0.6	22/01/2026	90	Internal peer review	Charalampos Thanopoulos (AGROKNOW) & Marina Georga (AGROKNOW)
V0.7	23/01/2026	95	Comments review	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO)
V1.0	10/02/2026	100	Final version	Grigorios Matenoglou (RAINNO), Christina Dimitriou (RAINNO), Iosif Vourvachis (RAINNO), Eleni Stogiannou (RAINNO), Meropi Koutsounaki (RAINNO)

EFRA Consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Number	Short name	Country
1	AGROKNOW IKE	AGROKNOW	EL
2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CSR	IT
3	STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	SU	SE
4	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
5	JAKALA S.p.A. S.B.	JAKALA	IT
6	AGRIVI DOO ZA PROIZVODNJU TRGOVINUI USLUGE	AGRIVI DOO	HR
7	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RAINNO	EL
8	SGS ROMANIA SA	SGS ROMANIA	RO
9	MOY PARK LTD	MOY PARK	UK

Table of Contents

<i>Glossary of terms and abbreviations used</i>	9
<i>Executive Summary</i>	10
1. Requirements	11
2. DEC Methodology and Approach	12
2.1. Progress towards Objectives and Time Plan	12
2.2. DEC Methodology	13
2.2.1. Data Management, Ethics and Gender Equality	14
3. Communication and Dissemination Channels, Tools and Activities	16
3.1. Branding and Material	16
3.2. Banners	16
3.2.1. Brochures.....	17
3.3. EFRA Website	18
3.4. Social Media Platforms	20
3.5. e-Newsletter and e-mail Campaigns	22
3.6. Multimedia	24
3.6.1. Promotional Videos	24
3.6.2. Podcast Series.....	25
3.7. Multiplier Campaigns	25
3.7.1. Press Releases.....	25
3.7.2. Interviews	26
3.8. Latest Publications	27
3.8.1. Scientific Publications	27
3.8.2. Technical Publications	28
3.8.3. Best Practices.....	32
3.8.4. Discussion papers	33
3.8.5. Sectoral Data and Prediction reports.....	34
3.9. Standards and Policy Publications	35
3.9.1. White papers	35
3.10. Ecosystem Building	35
3.10.1. Participation in commercial and trade events with booth	36
3.10.2. Participation in conferences	39
3.10.3. Joint events with relevant EU-funded projects.....	44
3.10.4. Meeting with Advisory Board	47
3.10.5. Industry-oriented & Scientific workshops and/or webinars.....	47
4. Monitoring and Evaluation	49
4.1. KPI Status	49
5. Exploitation and IPR Management	51
5.1. Exploitation Methodology	51

5.1.1.	Cycle 1: Investigate - IPR Baseline and Partner Expectations	51
5.1.2.	Cycle 2: Co-create – Continuous Mapping and Portfolio Development	52
5.1.3.	Cycle 3: Accelerate – Portfolio Validation and Sustainability Planning.....	52
5.2.	Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and Unique Value Proposition (UVP)	53
5.2.1.	The Nine Key Exploitable Results	53
5.3.	Exploitation Pathways	54
5.4.	EFRA’s Market Analysis, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	56
5.4.1.	Market Analysis	56
5.4.2.	Exploitation Roadmap: 24-Month Post-Project Plan	58
5.4.3.	Sustainability Mechanisms and Institutional Arrangements	59
5.5.	IPR Strategy	60
5.5.1.	Background Intellectual Property and Access Rights.....	60
5.5.2.	Foreground Intellectual Property and Ownership	60
5.5.3.	Protection of Results: Patents, Trade Secrets, and Copyright	60
5.5.4.	Patent Landscape and Freedom to Operate.....	61
5.5.5.	Data Protection and Confidentiality	61
5.6.	Positioning EFRA for Long-Term Impact	62
6.	Next Steps	63
6.1.	Refinement of Key Exploitable Results	63
6.2.	Strategic Partnership Development and Ecosystem Consolidation	63
6.3.	Dissemination and Visibility Beyond M36	63
6.4.	Sustainability Mechanisms and Business Model Implementation.....	64
6.5.	Technology Transfer and Capacity Building	65
6.6.	Monitoring Post-Project Impact and Outcomes.....	65
7.	Conclusion.....	66
7.1.	Synthesis of DEC Achievements	66
7.2.	Scientific and Technological Contributions	66
7.3.	Policy Alignment and Contribution to EU Strategic Objectives	67
7.4.	Ecosystem Building and Network Effects.....	67
7.5.	Remaining Challenges and Future Research Directions	67
7.6.	Recommendations for Stakeholders	68
7.7.	Final Reflections	68
Annex I	70
Annex II	71

List of Figures

Figure 1: EFRA’s DEC Phases	13
Figure 2: EFRA’s Ecosystem building.....	14
Figure 3: Use Case Banner Designs	16
Figure 4: Banner for Synergy Days 2024 & 2025.....	17
Figure 5: EFRA poster	17
Figure 6: Brochures	17
Figure 7: Web site analytics - Brochures.....	18
Figure 8: Snapshot from Google Analytics of EFRA website (audience)	19
Figure 9: Snapshot from Facebook Ad Performance	19
Figure 10: Bounce Rate	20
Figure 11: Blog posts.....	20
Figure 12: Social media accounts of EFRA.....	20
Figure 13: Facebook Ad Campaign for page followers.....	21
Figure 14: Social Media Performance Overview	22
Figure 15: Newsletter status	23
Figure 16: Sample of EFRA LinkedIn Newsletters	23
Figure 17: Snapshots of the EFRA video.....	24
Figure 18: EFRA Podcast on Spotify	25
Figure 19: Interview at Synergy Days 2025	26
Figure 20: Best Practices by WFSR (left) and JAKALA (right).....	32
Figure 21: EFRA Discussion Paper for the Period M25-M36, by Agroknow (left) and SGS Digicomply (right).....	33
Figure 22: Some of the sectoral data & prediction reports published in the period M25-M36 by SGS Digicomply (left), Agroknow (center) and WFSR (right)	35
Figure 23: EFRA’s participation in GFSI 2025	36
Figure 24: Presentation of the EFRA workshop on Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud in the NAFS event, Setp’25	37
Figure 25: EFRA’s participation in BEYOND 2025.....	38
Figure 26: EFRA booth & Pitch Talk at Synergy Days 2025	39
Figure 27: Workshop titled “Business models for AI-powered platforms in bioeconomy and food chains”, co-organized by EFRA during Synergy Days 2025	39
Figure 28: Key poultry and egg production industry players exhibiting at the IPPE 2025 event (28-30 January 2025, Atlanta, USA) and visited by Agroknow for engagement in the EFRA network	40
Figure 29: SGS Digicomply, representing EFRA in Global Food Safety Summit 2025.....	41
Figure 30: SGS Digicomply, representing EFRA in DIFSC 2025	42
Figure 31: SGS Digicomply, representing EFRA in FoodWorX 2025	42
Figure 32: JAKALA, representing EFRA in Semeval 2025.....	43
Figure 33: JAKALA, representing EFRA in JURIX 2025	43
Figure 34: Two EFRA posters from ECIR 2025 authored by CNR	44
Figure 35: Practical hands-on session on using AI-powered risk forecasting during the joint workshop held on 5 February 2025.	45
Figure 36: Snapshot from the interactive workshop with HOLIFOOD, by Agroknow	45
Figure 37: Presentation used to collect user feedback for the evaluation of the EFRA decision-support tools on Flock Performance Outlier Detection and Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting.	46
Figure 38: Presentation used to collect user feedback for the evaluation of the EFRA decision-support tool on Pest Prediction & Feedback Dashboard.....	47
Figure 39: Announcement of SemEval Task 9, “The Food Hazard Detection Challenge,” organised and supported by the EFRA project (SU and Agroknow).....	48
Figure 40: KERs Inventory & IPR.....	70

List of tables

Table 1: Target groups and their key messages.....	14
Table 2: Press Releases	25
Table 3: List of EFRA scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	27
Table 4: List of EFRA publications in scientific conferences.....	28
Table 5: List of EFRA Technical Publications/Articles (M25-M36)	29

Table 6: List of EFRA’s technical blog contributions in related sites (M25-M36).....	29
Table 7: Sectoral data & prediction reports for M25-M36	34
Table 8: D&C KPIs - M36 status.....	49
Table 9: EFRA’s KERs BFMULO Matrix.....	55
Table 10: AGROKNOW KPIs.....	71
Table 11: CNR KPIs	71
Table 12: SU KPIs.....	72
Table 13: WFSR KPIs.....	72
Table 14: JAKALA (ex-MAIZE) KPIs	73
Table 15: AGRIVI KPIs.....	73
Table 16: RAINNO KPIs.....	74
Table 17: SGS KPIs.....	75
Table 18: MOY KPIs	75

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
DEC plan	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan
DSSC	Data Space Support Centre
EASE	European Association of Science Editors
EC DGs	European Commission Directorates-General
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
fiin	Food Industry Intelligence Network
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFSI	Global Food Safety Initiative
HPC	High-performance computing
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreements
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
QR	Quick Response
SAGER	Sex and Gender Equity in Research
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SOSTAC	Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Actions and Control
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The EFRA project is dedicated to addressing emerging food risks through advanced analytics and artificial intelligence. It has demonstrated substantial progress in its dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) activities. Through a coordinated, multi-channel approach encompassing social media, newsletters, and multimedia resources, EFRA has successfully engaged a diverse range of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry representatives, and the broader public. Over the last 12 months, the project has exceeded several key performance indicators, underscoring strong engagement and effective knowledge transfer.

A central element of EFRA's strategy has been its active participation in scientific conferences, industry exhibitions, and collaborative events, where the project has presented its innovative solutions to current food safety challenges. Key outputs, which include peer-reviewed publications and technical deliverables, demonstrate EFRA's contributions to food risk prediction, decision-support tools, and sustainable operational practices. These achievements collectively support the project's overarching objective of strengthening the ecosystem that underpins food safety and public health.

As EFRA finished its third year, the project refined its approach, incorporating feedback from the mid-term review. This updated and last DEC plan integrates new use cases, such as the assessment of mycotoxin risks in animal feed, and expands the project's commitment to sustainability through increased reliance on digital communication materials. These adjustments reflect a continued emphasis on resource efficiency and environmentally responsible practices.

This final deliverable (D6.1.4) provides strategic guidance to all EFRA partners, consolidating the methodologies used to maximize the impact of the project's DEC activities. As the project concludes, this document also outlines the measures established to amplify EFRA's results and support the implementation of a comprehensive sustainability strategy, ensuring the long-term uptake and continued value of its outcomes beyond the project's lifetime.

1. Requirements

The present Deliverable 6.1.4 – Final Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report (DEC Report) has been developed within the framework of Task 6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation & Community Engagement, as well as Task 6.2 Building & Engaging a Public-Private Network on Risk Prediction and Task 6.3 Involvement in Industry Groups & Networks under WP6 – Generating Impact. Building on the foundations established in DEC Plan V1 (M3), V2 (M12), and V3 (M24), this final deliverable consolidates all advancements achieved during the complete implementation period of the EFRA project, with a particular focus on activities carried out from M24 to M36.

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation actions undertaken by the consortium and illustrates how EFRA's results, tools, and innovations have been promoted, transferred, and positioned for long-term impact. It presents the culmination of the project's awareness-raising efforts, summarising both the strategies adopted and the outcomes they delivered. The document also revisits the project's key target groups and describes how communication channels, messaging, and engagement tools were refined and deployed throughout the project's final year.

The scope of this deliverable is intentionally broad, aiming to secure the continued visibility and uptake of EFRA's methodologies and results among stakeholders from industry, academia, public authorities, and regulatory bodies. Beyond dissemination and communication, the document outlines the final exploitation strategy, detailing the pathways for post-project adoption, scalability, and sustainable use of EFRA's outputs.

As the concluding document in this series, Deliverable 6.1.4 serves as the definitive reference for all DEC-related activities undertaken over the lifespan of the project. It reports on the achievement of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the Grant Agreement and highlights the measures put in place to support the project's sustainability strategy beyond M36.

The document is structured into eight chapters, presenting the final DEC objectives, the evolution of the strategy across the project's duration, the outcomes of stakeholder engagement, and the tools, channels, and materials employed to ensure effective dissemination, communication, and exploitation of EFRA's results.

2. DEC Methodology and Approach

Since the launch of the EFRA project and after three years of coordinated effort in implementing, DEC plan has resulted in substantial progress and measurable impact. Across the project's full duration, the DEC plan has provided a strategic and coherent framework for expanding the EFRA ecosystem, strengthening visibility of project activities, and maximising influence across scientific, policy, industrial, and public domains.

Throughout this period, EFRA has consistently applied a targeted and integrated set of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication measures, ensuring that project visibility has translated into tangible value for stakeholders. The multi-channel approach, which has been refined and enhanced during the final year, has remained fully aligned with GDPR principles as outlined in the Data Management Plan (D7.2) and has upheld the project's commitment to gender equality and responsible research practices in all social and ethical considerations.

As the project concludes, these actions collectively demonstrate how EFRA's DEC strategy has supported the long-term positioning, accessibility, and future uptake of the project's outputs.

2.1. Progress towards Objectives and Time Plan

Dissemination Objectives: Over the full duration of the EFRA project, the dissemination strategy has continued to play a central role in sharing the project's scientific and technological advances—including its predictive models, decision-support tools, and methodological innovations. With a strong commitment to Open Science, EFRA has ensured that its outputs remain widely accessible to the research community, industry stakeholders, and public authorities.

The dissemination objectives established in earlier versions of the plan (D6.1.1, D6.1.2, and D6.1.3) have been fully applied and refined, guiding the systematic promotion of EFRA's results. In this final phase, dissemination efforts have focused on consolidating published knowledge, expanding the visibility of key outcomes, and supporting the long-term availability of EFRA's scientific contributions beyond the project's lifetime.

Communication Objectives: The communication strategy has, throughout the project, proven effective in maintaining a strong public presence and sustained engagement with EFRA's diverse stakeholder groups. By combining broad outreach activities with targeted messaging, the project has ensured that its developments, milestones, and results were communicated clearly and consistently.

In the final year, communication activities have been oriented toward amplifying awareness of EFRA's achievements, strengthening connections with the wider food safety and AI communities, and preparing the ground for continued visibility of EFRA's work after project completion.

Exploitation Objectives: As EFRA reaches its conclusion, exploitation activities have focused on translating project results into actionable pathways for adoption, commercial uptake, and long-term use. Throughout the project, these activities have evolved in parallel with the growing maturity of EFRA's datasets, models, and tools, ensuring that the practical value of each output is effectively captured.

In this final stage, the exploitation strategy consolidates the mechanisms for enabling stakeholders—industry actors, regulatory bodies, technology providers, and researchers—to integrate EFRA's results into their operations and decision-making processes. This ensures that the project's innovations can continue to generate impact well beyond M36.

Time Plan: The DEC plan was originally structured into four sequential phases (Figure 1), each designed to build on the achievements of the previous one to ensure cumulative and sustainable impact. Over the course of the project, all phases (project architecture development, awareness building, and the "Raising Cognition") have now been fully implemented.

In the final year, the consortium successfully carried out the "**Multiplier Effect**" phase, during which EFRA's results were consolidated, amplified, and strategically disseminated to maximise visibility and long-term

relevance. This concluding phase focused on broad stakeholder outreach, enhanced knowledge transfer, and the final positioning of EFRA's outputs to ensure continued uptake and impact beyond the project's lifetime.

Figure 1: EFRA's DEC Phases

2.2. DEC Methodology

Throughout the full duration of the EFRA project, the DEC methodology has provided a structured, coherent, and progressively refined approach to ensuring the effective dissemination, communication, and exploitation of project results. As the project concludes, this final deliverable consolidates the methodologies applied across all phases and highlights how these have supported the achievement of EFRA's impact objectives.

EFRA has consistently implemented a multi-actor, transdisciplinary methodology, drawing on insights from case studies, ecosystem dialogues, and continuous engagement with stakeholders across the food safety, research, and policy domains. This approach has enabled the consortium to integrate expertise from diverse scientific and industrial fields, ensuring that the project's outputs are both technically robust and practically relevant. The ecosystem-building framework (Figure 2), which has been presented in earlier deliverable version (D6.1.2), has served as a guiding structure for aligning technical developments with stakeholder needs and ensuring broad relevance and applicability.

Over the final reporting period, the DEC methodology has focused on consolidating stakeholder relationships, strengthening knowledge transfer mechanisms, and supporting the transition from project results to long-term uptake. Target groups defined in earlier iterations (D6.1.1, D6.1.2, D6.1.3) (see Table 1) have been consistently engaged using tailored key messages, ensuring that EFRA's outcomes were communicated with clarity, relevance, and alignment to each audience's needs. These groups continued to serve as the foundation for the project's outreach strategy.

In D6.1.4, the DEC methodology also reflects the shift toward sustainability and post-project continuity. Emphasis has been placed on supporting exploitation pathways, amplifying communication outputs, and ensuring the availability and accessibility of EFRA's tools, publications, and resources beyond project end. The methodology thus not only captures how DEC activities were implemented but also establishes a framework for the continued relevance and impact of EFRA's results after M36.

Figure 2: EFRA’s Ecosystem building

Table 1: Target groups and their key messages

Target Groups	Relevant Actors	Key Messages
Academic & Research organisations	Universities, faculties and research institutes of ICT, Engineering, Agriculture and sciences, academic staff	Utilise EFRA’s outputs for enhancing scientific knowledge on extreme data’s utilisation for prediction of future food risks
Policy makers & regulators	Local, regional and national authorities (e.g., ministries and governments), Standardisation organisations (ISO, ETSI, etc.) and EC DGs, units and regulatory agencies (e.g., EFSA, FDA)	Roadmap and design principles towards transforming the way food risk prevention takes place and fostering the EU’s provision for a more resilient, green and digital recovery
Data scientists and data analysts	Parties interested in extreme scale heterogeneous multi-lingual datasets and an energy efficient HPC infrastructure on which to assess, validate, and deploy AI models targeting use cases of high social and economic significance (i.e., food safety)	Adopt and embrace EFRA Data Hub & Analytics Powerhouse in the food sector, unlocking multi-level and multi-sectoral benefits
Food System Stakeholders	Food processors, packagers, distributors, retailers, farmers and farm advisors interested in predicting and monitoring emerging food safety risks and acting a-priori to mitigate them	Exploit data driven innovations and improved data access to maximise performance, efficiency and stable profit increase
Food Safety Experts	Food safety experts that need to stay informed on current and emerging food safety risks by accessing a large variety of data sources appropriately translated in their language and aligned with standard taxonomies	Reduce the economic damage from product recalls and maximise the benefits via the exploitation of advanced decision-making tools”
General Public	Consumers and their associations, NGOs and citizens	Gain insights on addressing societal challenges that COVID-19 pandemic brought associated with food safety and quality fraud

2.2.1. Data Management, Ethics and Gender Equality

Data Management: The EFRA project includes the collection and processing of data within the scope of its dissemination and communication activities. All data generated and utilized in these activities fully comply

with the GDPR and consider social and ethical considerations, including privacy and human rights. Data access, protection, and privacy standards adhere to both national legislation and EU regulations.

In cases where sensitive data is collected, the consortium ensures that such data will be anonymized wherever possible, securely stored for the duration of the project, and destroyed upon project completion. When full anonymization is not feasible, the project will rigorously apply the principles of personal data protection set out in Article 5(1) of the GDPR. A dedicated Data Management Plan (D7.2), established by M6, outlines a comprehensive framework to guarantee secure data collection, processing, and storage protocols.

Ethics and Gender Equality: Stakeholder engagement, participatory processes, and feedback loops are central to EFRA. Ethical and gender considerations are embedded throughout these activities, particularly regarding stakeholder selection, informed consent for participation, and the handling of personal data.

The consortium strictly upholds principles of non-discrimination based on race, religion, or gender. All partners adhere to the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, ensuring equal opportunities and gender balance within the project team. Gender balance will also be a criterion in stakeholder selection.

For dissemination activities (WP6), particular attention has been paid to: (i) Reporting sample characteristics by gender, sex, and relevant intersecting variables, with transparency regarding the collection of gender identity information while avoiding undue emphasis on gender differences, (ii) disaggregating results by sex and gender, presenting both positive and negative findings, (iii) ensuring gender variations are appropriately reflected in tables, figures, and conclusions and (iv) following the SAGER publication guidelines (EASE, 2016) where applicable.

Moreover, WP7 actively integrated the gender dimension throughout the project, promoting gender balance in research and decision-making processes, including the composition of evaluation panels and advisory boards. These measures aim to foster women's empowerment and fully align with Horizon Europe requirements (EU, 2021).

3. Communication and Dissemination Channels, Tools and Activities

3.1. Branding and Material

EFRA's communication material such as logo, motto, brand book, the project presentation, templates for various uses (e.g. presentations, deliverables etc.), roll-up banners and brochures have been presented in previous iterations. In the last 12 months of the project, various additional communication materials have been added to EFRA's arsenal.

3.2. Banners

Four banner designs were developed by RAINNO during the period M25-36, including one project banner and **one** banner for each use case (Figure 3). Each design presents the name of the relevant use case together with its key objective. In addition, the banners display the lead and technical or scientific partners, the consortium and EFRA logos, the project's website (in both textual form and via a QR code), social media references, and the EU emblem.

Figure 3: Use Case Banner Designs

Three banners were designed for the participation of EFRA at Synergy Days 2024, while **one** banner was developed for the Synergy Days 2025 (Figure 4). Furthermore, RAINNO designed and printed an additional **poster** (Figure 5) highlighting key project benefits. Overall, since the beginning of the project, **eight banners and one poster** have been produced, clearly exceeding the initial KPI target of four.

Figure 4: Banner for Synergy Days 2024 & 2025

Figure 5: EFRA poster

Figure 6: Brochures

3.2.1. Brochures

Five digital brochures have been designed by RAIN (one for project and four for each use case) with the contribution of use case leaders (Figure 6). Each brochure presents the use case name and its main objective. It outlines the specific challenge addressed, it explains how EFRA responds to it and highlights key elements of the methodology. It also shows how the use case contributes to the overall EFRA vision and goals. A contact person from the leading partner is included with relevant details. Finally, a standardised back page provides a project overview, consortium logos, social media links, the website, and the EU emblem. Overall, five different brochures have been designed during the project. The online brochures are located on the [EFRA website](#) in the dedicated section. According to the Google Analytics of the EFRA website the total views of the online brochures (corresponding KPI: “Scans of QR codes redirecting to a virtual brochure”) for the last year of the project stands at **1,377** while the total views for the whole duration of EFRA sums up to **1,412** (Figure 7), with a KPI target of 1,000.

Figure 7: Web site analytics - Brochures

3.3. EFRA Website

The EFRA website was launched in M2 and has been constantly updated with public dissemination deliverables, and relevant content (news, editorials, videos, workshops and demos events, press releases, printed material, scientific and other publications, etc.) for key stakeholder groups that wish to be informed with EFRA’s activities and results. During the last 12 Months, EFRA’s website has been updated with:

- Scientific and conference publications
- Articles & Reports
- Blog posts with various news and relevant content from the partners
- Update of the “Videos” page³ with the recent project’s videos
- Update of the “Newsletter” page⁴ with the new newsletter issues

By M24, the website has recorded **1,323** unique visitors and the total number up to M36 is **6,985** (Figure 8). This remains below our target of 20,000 unique visitors, a target highly optimistic given the average outreach of research projects with small consortia and no Open Calls.

The discrepancy can be attributed primarily to changes in audience behaviour and digital content consumption patterns that shifted during the project period. As online engagement increasingly moved towards social media platforms rather than direct website visits, achieving high traffic numbers through the project website alone proved more challenging than anticipated.

To mitigate this, the consortium took targeted corrective measures, focusing on expanding reach through coordinated social media campaigns. To enhance visibility, a Facebook traffic campaign ran from 4 November to 25 December, with short breaks in between (Figure 8). Around **151,900** Facebook users saw the campaign at least one time (Figure 9). The main objective was to drive website traffic and increase awareness. Facebook Ads Manager registered about **586 clicks** (to the EFRA landing page, while Google Analytics 4 (GA4) showed a noticeably lower number of unique visitors for the same period. We worked extensively to understand and resolve this gap, applying every fix recommended in the official Meta^{5,6} and Google⁷ documentation as well

³ <https://efraproject.eu/videos/>

⁴ <https://efraproject.eu/newsletters/>

⁵ <https://www.facebook.com/business/help/511923449323749?id=354406972049255>

⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/business/help/147965221941551>

⁷ <https://support.google.com/analytics/thread/261326852/facebook-source-problem-in-ga4?hl=en>

as guidance from trusted analytics experts^{8,9,10}. Even so, the numbers could not be aligned.

This outcome is largely due to how differently the two platforms track and interpret activity. Facebook counts every click based on its own attribution rules and server-side logic, whereas GA4 measures sessions and users through browser-based signals that can be affected by cookies being blocked, privacy settings, incomplete page loads, and other limits introduced by modern devices and operating systems. Users may also leave the page before GA4 has time to record their visit.

Figure 8: Snapshot from Google Analytics of EFRA website (audience)

In general, while the campaign contributed to outreach, its impact on the KPI of 20.000 unique visitors remains limited, highlighting that the original target was highly optimistic for a Horizon Europe RIA project. The social media campaigns significantly increased awareness and interactions with the project’s content, generating strong engagement metrics, which complemented the website’s role as a reference repository rather than a daily engagement hub.

Figure 9: Snapshot from Facebook Ad Performance

Additionally, the website’s bounce rate, the second relevant KPI, for the period M13-M24 is **44,09%** The target for this KPI is to keep the percentage under 50%. The overall bounce rate of the EFRA website for the whole duration of the project is **54,56%** (Figure 10). Another website KPI, as indicated in the Grant Agreement

⁸ <https://www.ruleranalytics.com/blog/analytics/facebook-ads-google-analytics-discrepancy/>

⁹ <https://matomo.org/blog/2025/07/what-is-server-side-tracking/>

¹⁰ <https://measureschool.com/tracking-facebook-ads-in-google-analytics-4/>

is the number of published blog posts on the website. The total number of published blog posts is 62, with overachieving the KPI target of 50 (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Bounce Rate

Figure 11: Blog posts

3.4. Social Media Platforms

EFRA has a strong social media presence on five different platforms (Figure 12), to reach out and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To monitor the social media accounts and ensure their effectiveness, a number of metrics have been tracked, in line with the KPIs claimed in the Grant Agreement.

Figure 12: Social media accounts of EFRA

Audience: Measuring our social media audience provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of our social media strategy and the visibility of the project. Currently, the total audience on all the platforms is **2.273** overachieving the target of 2.000. A Facebook ad campaign aimed at increasing our page followers ran from 30 September 2025 to 31 October 2025 (Figure 13). The campaign successfully generated **808** new followers and reached **59.750** unique Facebook users. This initiative significantly contributed to expanding the project’s social media presence and engagement, strengthening visibility and awareness among the target audience.

Figure 13: Facebook Ad Campaign for page followers

Posts: It refers to the number of posts, both the original content uploaded by the EFRA accounts and the repost of the relevant-to-the-project posts coming from the partners’ accounts. The total goal for this KPI is 200, and currently, we have posted **524**, clearly overachieving the KPI and demonstrating a consistently high level of online communication.

Interactions: The sum of likes/reactions, comments, shares, retweets and clicks of all the posts for LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and SlideShare. For YouTube we consider the views of the videos on EFRA channel. This metric reflects the organic engagement in social media platforms with the audience and the relevant KPI target is 15.000 by the end of the project. Currently, the total number of interactions is **16,181**. The analytics tools of the platforms have been used to collect the relevant data monthly. An overview of the Social Media Performance can be found at Figure 14.

Figure 14: Social Media Performance Overview

3.5. e-Newsletter and e-mail Campaigns

From January 2025 (M25) to December 2025 (M36), **two** more newsletter issues have been released as planned (Figure 15).

36-MONTH STATUS OF NEWSLETTER

Figure 15: Newsletter status

All the newsletter issues are available even for non-subscribers and can be found on the project's website in the dedicated section¹¹. While EFRA maintains a regular email newsletter, additional issues are also published on LinkedIn ¹²(started in April 2025) to reach a broader professional audience Figure 16). The LinkedIn newsletter issues focus primarily on knowledge transfer related to EFRA’s core research areas, such as food safety, AI, and data analytics. Their purpose is to disseminate thematic insights rather than provide regular project updates. LinkedIn’s platform enhances visibility, encourages knowledge sharing, and strengthens connections with stakeholders. Regarding performance tracking, the relevant KPI target of the newsletter subscribers is 1.000 and their total interactions are 3.000, as claimed in the Grant Agreement. As interactions, we consider all the newsletter opens and the clicks inside them. Currently, the subscribers total to **632** (209 unique email addresses and **455** LinkedIn subscribers), while the total number of interactions is **2,129** (1436 in email issues and **693** in the LinkedIn issue).

The number of newsletter subscriptions and user interactions remained below the expected target, reflecting limited uptake among key stakeholder groups. Despite the systematic and consistent dissemination through consortium and social media channels, the quantitative KPI for newsletter subscriptions was not achieved. However, the underlying communication objective of *ensuring regular, relevant, and broad dissemination of project results* was largely fulfilled through a set of alternative outreach activities and the coordinated use of both project and partner communication channels.

Figure 16: Sample of EFRA LinkedIn Newsletters

¹¹ <https://efraproject.eu/newsletters/>

¹² <https://www.linkedin.com/newsletters/insights-on-ai-food-safety-7318534613683847169/>

3.6. Multimedia

3.6.1. Promotional Videos

To enhance outreach and engagement, EFRA has developed a variety of multimedia materials aimed at presenting the project in a clear, accessible, and engaging manner. These materials serve as valuable tools for explaining complex concepts, promoting project activities, and attracting wider audiences. The project has set a KPI target of **five** videos. As of December 2025, a total of 12 videos has been published on EFRA's official YouTube channel, with 4 released during the period M25-M36. Videos reported in previous editions of the deliverable are the **official project video**¹³ and **two interviews** of RAINNO and Agroknow about the project. During the last year of EFRA, the consortium produced and uploaded on the project's YouTube channel the following videos:

- A series of **6** interview episodes¹⁴, organised and hosted by RAINNO, featuring experts from the EFRA consortium. These interviews cover key topics including the EFRA platform, business models, and relevant to the project technologies.
- **1** interview by RAINNO, during Synergy Days 2025.
- **3** videos dedicated to the EFRA Use Cases.

Currently, the total number of unique views across **all videos sums up to 13** (Figure 17). These video materials are designed to be self-explanatory and suitable for various audiences, including policymakers, researchers, end-users, and the public. Interviews have been recorded during the Plenary Meeting in Thessaloniki (June 2025), offering authentic insights into the project's progress and perspectives from various partners.

Figure 17: Snapshots of the EFRA video

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nLLoTXVWFws>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLevNctkbVRw6sF5OdHJMxWrinof2gF-b9>

3.6.2. Podcast Series

EFRA has produced **two podcast series with a total of 10 episodes** to diversify the project’s communication content and address auditory learning preferences, achieving the KPI target. By M12, Agroknow released the first **4** episodes on YouTube¹⁵, offering insights into digital food safety through discussions with field experts. During M25–M36, the remaining **6** episodes were published on the project’s Spotify¹⁶ channel (Figure 18). The series, titled *“The EFRA Podcast: Insights on AI & Food Safety,”* follows an interview format and focuses on the EFRA Platform, its modules, the business model, and key technologies used in the project, such as AI model training, natural language processing, explainable AI, and related topics. The episodes are actively promoted through the project’s website, newsletter, and social media accounts, contributing significantly to raising awareness, sharing knowledge, and highlighting the relevance of EFRA’s work to diverse stakeholder groups.

Figure 18: EFRA Podcast on Spotify

3.7. Multiplier Campaigns

3.7.1. Press Releases

Over the lifetime of the project, a total of eight press releases is planned. By M36, **we achieved our goal of 8 press releases** to be successfully published. For the period M25-M36, **4 Press Releases** were published, reaching to a total of 8, which was the target value of the project. These include press releases issued by Agroknow, CNR, AGRIVI, RAINNO and SGS (Table 2).

Table 2: Press Releases

PARTNER	Number	Link
Press Releases for M25-M36		
AGROKNOW	1	https://efraproject.eu/efra-project-makes-the-data-analytics-marketplace-available-to-the-community-a-horizon-europe-outcome-supporting-food-risk-data-ai-and-collaboration/

¹⁵ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLOvYtUCtuBvCdrXrK_sixYwH49hKxJQvu

¹⁶ <https://open.spotify.com/show/6eS2YtbR4Yr8KJW2FZYSFO?si=UuxVmFdVQ96FLNIevME8sw>

AGRIVI	1	https://www.agrivi.com/hr/novosti/hrvatska-tehnologija-u-sluzbi-sigurnosti-hrane-agrivi-ulazi-u-drugu-fazu-razvoja-ai-modela-za-detekciju-stetnika/
SGS	2	i. https://www.prlog.org/13084273-chatting-with-food-regulations-how-efra-uses-the-sgs-digicomply-ai-copilot.html ii. https://www.digicomply.com/blog/sgs-digicomply-to-present-at-foodworx-2025-augmenting-food-safety-through-artificial-intelligence
Previous Press Releases (M1-M24)		
CNR	1	https://www.isti.cnr.it/images/pdf/isti-news/IstiNews_2023-13.pdf
RAINNO	3	i. https://efraproject.eu/efras-first-press-release/ ii. https://efraproject.eu/efras-first-press-release/ iii. https://thesstoday.gr/%CE%B1%CF%83%CF%86%CE%AC%CE%BB%CE%B5%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CF%84%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%86%CE%AF%CE%BC%CF%89%CE%BD-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%81%CF%89%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%8A%CE%BA%CF%8C-%CE%AD%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%BF-efra/#goog_rewarded

3.7.2. Interviews

Since the start of the project, the consortium has given **10** interviews, meeting the KPI target. These interviews promoted key project activities and made use of diverse channels and communication approaches. During M1-M24, **6** interviews were provided by Agroknow, Stockholm University, AGRIVI and RAINNO. Details on these are included in previous deliverable versions. In the final year of EFRA, **4** additional interviews were delivered by RAINNO:

- “*Navigating Innovations and Bridging Gaps in Food Safety*”¹⁷, Position Magazine
- Interview at BEYOND TV¹⁸ during RAINNO’s participation at Beyond 2025
- Interview on the Synergy Portal website¹⁹ for EFRA’s presence at Synergy Days 2025
- Interview on business models²⁰ during Synergy Days 2025 (Figure 19)

Figure 19: Interview at Synergy Days 2025

¹⁷ <https://positio-magazine.eu/2025/01/navigating-innovations-and-bridging-gaps-in-food-safety/>

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PGGh4xmW5og>

¹⁹ <https://www.synergyportal.eu/latest-news/synergy-days-2025-efra>

²⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HJi-JHGourM&t=3s>

3.8. Latest Publications

EFRA has already produced several scientific, industry, standards and policy publications and practice abstracts as well as source code to influence a wide range of targeted stakeholders and to promote the project and its findings (see D6.1.2). A new series of the aforementioned publications stemming from EFRA's research and activities from M25 up to M36 is presented below. All publications implemented Open Access and open peer-review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science.

3.8.1. Scientific Publications

EFRA's goal was to publish at least **9 peer-reviewed scientific papers** in respected and highly rated open-access scientific journals and **12 publications in scientific conferences** (e.g. GFSI & Sustainable Foods) as means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project's work. This task has been undertaken by the coordinator (AGROKNOW) and university and research partners (CNR, SU, WFSR) and publications cover several fields of the work performed within the EFRA project. In addition, EFRA targeted to participate in **9 scientific conferences** during the lifespan of the project. In all those categories, EFRA overachieved by publishing **11 publications in peer-reviewed journals**, **19 publications in scientific conferences** and participated in **15 scientific conferences**.

From M25 up to M36 **7 more scientific publications** have been published from AGROKNOW, CNR, WFSR, JAKALA and SU (

Table 3), and **5 publication have been submitted to scientific conferences** (

Table 4) and are presented in the tables below.

Table 3: List of EFRA scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals

Title	Publication Date	Associated Partner	Journal
What Lies Behind Mycotoxin Presence in Animal Feed? A Case Study	Feb 2025	Agroknow	Journal of Food Protection ²¹
ChatGPT Versus Modest Large Language Models: An Extensive Study on Benefits and Drawbacks for Conversational Search	Feb 2025	CNR	IEEE Access ²²
Mind the Gap: From Plausible to Valid Self-Explanations in Large Language Models	Jul 2025	SU	Machine Learning ²³
Federated learning in food research	Aug 2025	WFSR	Journal of Agriculture and Food Research ²⁴
Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Deep Learning in Food: Challenges and Opportunities for Food Systems	Aug 2025	WFSR	Nature Food ²⁵

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfp.2025.100464>

²² <https://dx.doi.org/10.1109/access.2025.3529741>

²³ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-025-06838-6>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2025.102238>

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7289201/v1>

Neural Network Compression using Binarization and Few Full-Precision Weights	Oct 2025	CNR	Information Sciences ²⁶
Food safety trends across Europe: insights from the 392-million-entry CompreHensive European Food Safety (CHEFS) database	Nov 2025	WFSR	Food Control ²⁷

Table 4: List of EFRA publications in scientific conferences

Title	Date	Associated Partner	Conference	Type of Attendees
LR2: a Legal RAG for Legal Reasoning over Cases ²⁸	Mar 2025	JAKALA	Jurix 2025	Research Communities
Power- and Fragmentation-aware Online Scheduling for GPU Datacenters ²⁹	May 2025	CNR	25th IEEE International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud, and Internet Computing	Research Communities
BitsAndBites at SemEval-2025 Task 9: Improving Food Hazard Detection with Sequential Multitask Learning and Large Language Models ³⁰	Jul 2025	JAKALA	19th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval-2025)	Research Communities
SemEval-2025 Task 9: The Food Hazard Detection Challenge ³¹	Jul 2025	SU	19th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval-2025)	Research Communities
BrightCookies at SemEval-2025 Task 9: Exploring Data Augmentation ³²	Jul 2025	WFSR	19th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation	Research Communities

3.8.2. Technical Publications

Besides creating scientific publications, EFRA's target was to publish at least **12 technical publications/articles** and promote them via high-quality technical blog posts. For M25 to M36, **7 technical articles** have been published (Table 5), which achieved the total number of the target.

EFRA established a **target of 50 blog contributions** addressing technical advances in food risk prediction, AI, and related sectors. During the M25–M36 period, consortium partners published **25 new technical posts**. Additionally, this report captures **6 contributions published prior to M25** (during 2024) that were not included in the previous deliverable (D6.1.3). Consequently, the project has reached a cumulative **total of 52 contributions**, successfully exceeding the target. Table 6 details the titles and publication sites for all new entries, with the retrospective 2024 contributions listed at the end.

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2025.122251>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2025.111816>

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.3233/FAIA251614>

²⁹ <https://www.computer.org/csdl/proceedings-article/ccgrid/2025/093400a043/27Y6DtOHfZm>

³⁰ <https://aclanthology.org/2025.semeval-1.99/>

³¹ <https://aclanthology.org/2025.semeval-1.325/>

³² <https://aclanthology.org/2025.semeval-1.124/>

Table 5: List of EFRA Technical Publications/Articles (M25-M36)

Title	Publication Date	Associated Partner	Publication Site
Knowledge Extraction in the age of LLMs.	Feb 2025	JAKALA	https://efraproject.eu/knowledge-extraction-in-the-age-of-llms/
Predicting Corn Infections Using Weather Data and Machine Learning	May 2025	AGRIVI	https://zenodo.org/records/15632068
Blending Learning to Rank and Dense Representations for Efficient and Effective Cascades	Oct 2025	CNR	https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.16393
Exact Nearest-Neighbor Search on Energy-Efficient FPGA Devices	Oct 2025	CNR	https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.16736
A detailed technical report on "What's up with <i>Salmonella spp.</i> incidents: Exploration of Risks and Innovations in Food Safety"	Nov 2025	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/whats-up-with-salmonella-spp-incidents-exploration-of-risks-and-innovations-in-food-safety/
Human Mobility Datasets Enriched with Contextual and Social Dimensions	Dec 2025	CNR	https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.02333
Spatially-Enhanced Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Walkability and Urban Discovery	Dec 2025	CNR	https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.04790

Table 6: List of EFRA's technical blog contributions in related sites (M25-M36)

Title	Publication Date	Associated Partner	Publication Site
An EFRA-powered edition of the Incidents Forecast Trends Report for December 2024, covering 10 key food categories, including poultry and poultry meat products. The report examines the performance of our hazard trend forecasts for the top Biological, Chemical, Foreign Bodies, and Allergens Hazard Categories.	Jan 2025	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/monthly-forecasts-review-december/
Improving Information Retrieval: why dimensions matter in AI models	Jan 2025	CNR	https://link.medium.com/4LI7cWHSOPb
Can Smaller Language Models Compete with ChatGPT? A New Study Has the Answer	Feb 2025	CNR	https://medium.com/@beatrice.rapisarda/can-smaller-language-models-compete-with-chatgpt-a-new-study-has-the-answer-f8311c2cd0d2

The Evolution of Sparse Information Retrieval	May 2025	CNR	https://medium.com/@beatrice.rapisarda/the-evolution-of-sparse-information-retrieval-0857e5dcc761
Saving Energy Without Wasting Power: The Algorithm That Optimizes AI Datacenters	May 2025	CNR	https://medium.com/@beatrice.rapisarda/saving-energy-without-wasting-power-the-italian-algorithm-that-optimizes-ai-datacenters-39256e490637
Seismic: A Breakthrough Algorithm for Faster and More Interpretable AI Search	Oct 2025	CNR	https://medium.com/@beatrice.rapisarda/seismic-a-breakthrough-algorithm-for-faster-and-more-interpretable-ai-search-7a43412ecc5c
Can Sparse Neural Search Scale to 138 million Documents?	Feb 2026	CNR	https://medium.com/@beatrice.rapisarda/can-sparse-neural-search-scale-to-138-million-documents-0d0e95638dac
Advancing AI for Food Safety: Key Takeaways from the SemEval 2025 Food Hazard Detection Challenge	Feb 2025	SU	https://medium.com/@projectefra/advancing-ai-for-food-safety-key-takeaways-from-the-semeval-2025-food-hazard-detection-challenge-602735b220d4
A New Resource for Food Safety Research	May 2025	SU	https://medium.com/@projectefra/a-new-resource-for-food-safety-research-d243d7c93c73
When Your AI Explains Itself (And Gets It Wrong): Rethinking Trust in Language Models for Food Safety	Aug 2025	SU	https://medium.com/@projectefra/when-your-ai-explains-itself-and-gets-it-wrong-rethinking-trust-in-language-models-for-food-c521992ed474
Predicting pest occurrence with AI: an overview	Jan 2025	WFSR	https://medium.com/@projectefra/predicting-pest-occurrence-with-ai-an-overview-cbef1fe8bb4f
Unlocking Food Safety Insights with AI: How Large Language Models Help Extract Critical Information	Feb 2025	JAKALA	https://medium.com/@projectefra/unlocking-food-safety-insights-with-ai-how-large-language-models-help-extract-critical-information-9676552cdfd
AI Detecting Dangerous Foods: How a New Approach is Making Food Safer	Apr 2025	JAKALA	https://medium.com/@projectefra/ai-detecting-dangerous-foods-how-a-new-approach-is-making-food-safer-276cd45c2cc5
EFRA Platform: What We Learned Deploying a Distributed System on GKE with Terraform and Helm	Aug 2025	JAKALA	https://medium.com/@projectefra/efra-platform-what-we-learned-deploying-a-distributed-system-on-gke-with-terraform-and-helm-defedf3826f0
Smarter AI for Safer Food: How We Improved Food Hazard Detection at SemEval-2025	Feb 2026	JAKALA	https://medium.com/@projectefra/smarter-ai-for-safer-food-how-we-improved-food-hazard-detection-at-semeval-2025-0f38bab0a158?postPublishedType=repub
Building Trust from Farm to Fork: How QR Codes Are Empowering Consumers	Jan 2025	AGRIVI	https://medium.com/@projectefra/building-trust-from-farm-to-fork-how-qr-codes-are-empowering-consumers-3534f177de3d

Food Safety Starts on the Farm	Mar 2025	AGRIVI	https://medium.com/@projectefra/food-safety-starts-on-the-farm-e7cf05754efc
AGRIVI Enhances Pest Detection Through EFRA Field Trials: Real Farmers, Real Results	Feb 2026	AGRIVI	https://medium.com/@projectefra/agrivi-enhances-pest-detection-through-efra-field-trials-real-farmers-real-results-1e7b275b949d
Revolutionizing Food Regulations with AI: The Latest Breakthroughs Will Shock You	Mar 2025	SGS	https://medium.com/@projectefra/revolutionizing-food-regulations-with-ai-the-future-of-compliance-just-took-a-wild-turn-97853a2ddf47
Beyond the Hype: How Do We Really Know if an AI Summary is Good?	Nov 2025	SGS	https://medium.com/@projectefra/beyond-the-hype-how-do-we-really-know-if-an-ai-summary-is-good-d9992345781b
In an Age of AI, Why We're Trusting Human Experts	Nov 2025	SGS	https://medium.com/@projectefra/in-an-age-of-ai-why-were-trusting-human-experts-235bd36dc8b1
AI-Powered Regulatory Intelligence in the EFRA Project: Summarization and Conversational Access	Feb 2026	SGS	https://medium.com/@projectefra/ai-powered-regulatory-intelligence-in-the-efra-project-summarization-and-conversational-access-1cda67508303
Harnessing the DCCS Business Model Approach for EFRA's Digital Platform	May 2025	RAINNO	https://medium.com/@projectefra/harnessing-the-dssc-business-model-approach-for-efras-digital-platform-c5ff6f5d8e8a
Business Models for Data-Driven Platforms: Lessons from EFRA	Feb 2026	RAINNO	https://medium.com/@projectefra/business-models-for-data-driven-food-safety-platforms-lessons-from-efra-44913204f62d
From Grant to Legacy: IPR and Post-Project Sustainability in Horizon Europe	Feb 2026	RAINNO	https://medium.com/@projectefra/from-grant-to-legacy-ipr-and-post-project-sustainability-in-horizon-europe-f2bd8d0747c6
Blog contributions not reported in D6.1.3 (published up to M24)			
Monthly Forecasts Review: February	Mar 2024	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/monthly-forecasts-review-february/
What factors contribute to the evolution of Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) in Salmonella?	Jul 2024	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/what-factors-contribute-to-the-evolution-of-antimicrobial-resistance-amr-in-salmonella/
What's up with Salmonella spp incidents: Exploration of Risks and Innovations in Food Safety	Oct 2024	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/whats-up-with-salmonella-spp-incidents-exploration-of-risks-and-innovations-in-food-safety/
Why Aggregated Laboratory Testing Data Analytics are key to Preventing Costly Recalls	Oct 2024	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/dont-get-siloed-why-aggregated-laboratory-testing-data-analytics-are-key-to-preventing-costly-recalls/
When they start to share that data as an industry group, the real value emerges because you	Nov 2024	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/when-they-start-to-share-that-data-as-an-industry-group-the-real-value-emerges-because-

get a bigger picture of what's going on in the environment			you-get-a-bigger-picture-of-whats-going-on-in-the-environment/
Harnessing AI to Predict and Prevent Costly Recalls: Revisiting 3 Past Outbreaks	Dec 2024	AGROKNOW	https://www.foodakai.com/harnessing-ai-to-predict-and-prevent-costly-recalls-revisiting-3-past-outbreaks/

3.8.3. Best Practices

During the period M25-M36, **2 Best Practices** have been published by the EFRA Consortium (Figure 20), reaching to a **total number of 4**, surpassing the initial target of 3.

The first one that was prepared by WFSR, "**Best Practice Specification for Creating and Using a Domain-Specific Text Corpus for Relevant Document Identification**"³³, details the lifecycle of building the NYT Food Corpus [from New York Times archive collection (2010-2023), expert annotation with Eurostat-aligned relevance criteria, disagreement resolution, to BERT-based classification] yielding a reproducible dataset for food-related content filtering. Tailored for transparency and extensibility, it equips EFRA stakeholders with methodologies to curate high-quality corpora, enhancing data relevance in platform analytics and advancing exploitation in multilingual food safety monitoring. Communication efforts will promote its adoption through workshops and open-access publication.

Figure 20: Best Practices by WFSR (left) and JAKALA (right)

JAKALA prepared the second one, "**Best Practices for Ontology-Aware Retrieval in LLM-Based Systems**"³⁴, which provides essential guidelines for designing hybrid search indexes over ontologies such as AGROVOC and FoodOn, enabling efficient Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) in EFRA's semantic annotation pipelines for food safety incident analysis. Grounded in EFRA experimentation, it advocates retrieval-first principles, rich knowledge object indexing, and LLM-friendly outputs to boost accuracy and scalability in knowledge-intensive tasks, directly supporting the platform's exploitation through reusable, transparent AI

³³ <https://efraproject.eu/best-practice-specification-for-creating-and-using-a-domain-specific-text-corpus-for-relevant-document-identification/>

³⁴ <https://efraproject.eu/best-practices-for-ontology-aware-retrieval-in-llm-based-systems/>

infrastructures. This resource will be disseminated via the EFRA repository to empower developers and researchers in EU-funded food safety innovations.

3.8.4. Discussion papers

During the period of this deliverable (M25-M36), **2 discussion papers** have been published (Figure 21), reaching to a **total of 4** and achieving the initial target.

Figure 21: EFRA Discussion Paper for the Period M25-M36, by Agroknow (left) and SGS Digicomply (right)

On December 2025, Agroknow has published a discussion paper (Figure 21), titled **“AI for Resilient Food Systems and Risk Intelligence”**³⁵. This document serves as a roadmap for the digital transformation of global food safety, proposing a shift from reactive monitoring to a proactive, AI-driven prevention paradigm. Key pillars include the creation of a Common European Food Safety Data Space, the implementation of Trustworthy AI in line with the EU AI Act, and the use of large language models (LLMs) to automate regulatory compliance. The paper provides an actionable framework for policymakers and industry stakeholders to achieve a more resilient and sustainable food system over the next decade.

The same period (December 2025) SGS Digicomply published their discussion paper **“AI-Powered Risk Intelligence in Food Safety: From Prediction to Policy and Practice”**³⁶. The paper (Figure 21) explores how artificial intelligence can strengthen risk assessment and early warning across the food supply chain, from primary production to distribution. It examines the transition from traditional, reactive food safety controls to proactive, data-driven approaches that integrate diverse data sources and predictive analytics. The paper also discusses implications for regulators, industry, and consumers, highlighting how AI-enabled risk intelligence can inform evidence-based policymaking, support compliance, and improve overall public health protection.

³⁵ https://efraproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/EFRA-Discussion_Paper-AI-for-Resilient-Food-Systems.pdf

³⁶ <https://www.digicomply.com/hubfs/EFRA%20Discussion%20Paper%20AI%E2%80%90Powered%20Risk%20Intelligence%20in%20Food%20Safety%20From%20Prediction%20to%20Policy%20and%20Practice.pdf>

3.8.5. Sectoral Data and Prediction reports

During the period of this deliverable (M25-M36) **5 Sectoral Data and Prediction Reports** have been published from AGROKNOW, SGS and WFSR (Figure 22), thus achieving the target of **6 in total** for the EFRA project.

Table 7: Sectoral data & prediction reports for M25-M36

Title	Partner	Link
Monthly Food Risk Index – January 2025	Agroknow	https://www.foodakai.com/monthly-food-risk-index-january-2025-2/
<p><i>Summary: An EFRA-powered edition of Agroknow’s Monthly Food Risk Index for January 2025, offering a concise, data-driven view of food safety risks across 11 key product categories. The index combines hazard severity and incident probability to highlight emerging threats, with January showing persistently high risk in Eggs due to recurring Salmonella incidents and a notable rise in Fruits driven mainly by pesticide-related hazards such as chlorpyrifos. Supported by EFRA’s AI-enhanced analytics, the report provides actionable insights to help stakeholders anticipate risks and strengthen mitigation strategies.</i></p>		
Monthly Food Risk Index – February 2025	Agroknow	https://www.foodakai.com/monthly-food-risk-index-ferbruary-2025/
<p><i>Summary: An EFRA-supported edition of Agroknow’s Monthly Food Risk Index for February 2025, offering a concise view of food safety risks across 11 key product categories. Eggs remain the highest-risk category due to persistent Salmonella incidents, while fruits continue to show elevated pesticide-driven risk. Most other categories stay close to historical averages. Powered by EFRA’s AI-enhanced analytics, the report highlights the month’s emerging hazards and supports proactive risk-mitigation decisions.</i></p>		
Global Food Recall Index: Q1 2025 Sees Alarming Rise in Recalls for Meat, Cereals, and Fresh Produce	Agroknow	https://www.foodakai.com/global-food-recall-index-q1-2025-sees-alarming-rise-in-recalls-for-meat-cereals-and-fresh-produce/
<p><i>Summary: The report reveals notable shifts in food recall trends, with dairy products leading recall volumes due to microbiological contamination and handling issues, signalling ongoing cold-chain challenges. While recalls for beef, pork, cereals, and fresh produce were lower compared to Q1 2024, they are forecast to rise in Q2 2025, indicating emerging vulnerabilities. Additionally, egg and oils/fats recalls increased, partly due to supply chain disruptions like avian influenza, though these may stabilise later in the year. The Index provides quarterly risk insights to help stakeholders anticipate changing recall patterns in key food categories.</i></p>		
Integrating AI into Food Safety Workflows	SGS	https://efraproject.eu/integrating-ai-into-food-safety-workflows/
<p><i>Summary: The report highlights the increasing pressure on global food safety systems, driven by climate change, regulatory complexity, and persistent supply chain blind spots. It demonstrates how AI-enabled tools, particularly large language models, can support earlier detection of food safety risks, improve regulatory compliance, and strengthen data-driven decision-making. By integrating diverse data sources across the food system, the approach supports a shift from reactive incident management to proactive risk prevention. Within the EFRA project, SGS Digicomply illustrates how AI can contribute to a more resilient, transparent, and prevention-oriented European food safety ecosystem.</i></p>		
Food Safety and Cybersecurity	WFSR	https://efraproject.eu/food-safety-and-cybersecurity/
<p><i>Summary: The report maps the food sector’s cybersecurity maturity amid Industry 4.0 adoption, detailing threats from AI poisoning to supply-chain attacks, their cascading effects on safety operations, and pathways to resilience through integrated standards like IEC 62443 and NIST frameworks. Contextualized</i></p>		

for platforms like EFRA, it underscores governance harmonization and secure data sharing to safeguard traceability and predictive analytics, contributing measurable KPIs to the project's societal impact. Dissemination includes integration into EFRA's DEC channels for broad stakeholder uptake and long-term exploitation.

Figure 22: Some of the sectoral data & prediction reports published in the period M25-M36 by SGS Digicomply (left), Agroknow (center) and WFSR (right)

3.9. Standards and Policy Publications

3.9.1. White papers

During the period for this Deliverable (M25-M36) one White Paper has been published from WFSR titled "**Cybersecurity and Food Safety in Digital Platforms**"³⁷, achieving the target KPI. It analyses cyber-physical risks in data-driven systems like EFRA, linking threats such as ransomware and IoT manipulation to food integrity, supply continuity, and trust, with recommendations for secure-by-design governance aligned to NIS2 and ISO standards. Drawing on EFRA's pilot applications in poultry and pest alarms, it positions cybersecurity as foundational to resilient food safety platforms, informing the project's risk management and stakeholder engagement. It will be exploited via policy briefs and sector forums to amplify EFRA's impact on EU digital agri-food resilience.

3.10. Ecosystem Building

The development of a strong, interconnected food safety ecosystem involving the EFRA consortium, academic partners, and industry actors is a long-term undertaking. This effort is driven by two complementary goals: strengthening academic research on AI-based food risk prevention and demonstrating the commercial value of the EFRA platform to food-sector stakeholders and related industries. Taking an integrated and strategic approach, the EFRA consortium has carried out the following dissemination and outreach activities over the last 12 months (M25–M36):

- EFRA's participation with **4 booths** in relevant commercial and trade events.
- EFRA's participation in **8 conferences**.
- **2 Joint events** with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives.

³⁷ <https://efraproject.eu/white-paper-cybersecurity-and-food-safety-in-digital-platforms/>

- **1 scientific/data science** workshops and/or webinars.
- **1 dedicated session** at the annual GFSI/finn events.

3.10.1. Participation in commercial and trade events with booth

During the last 12 months (M25-M36) of EFRA, the consortium members have participated with a booth in **4 events**. The initial KPI target of 6 in total, has been overachieved, as the total number add up to 12.

Agroknow participated in the Global Food Safety Initiative (GFSI) 2025 Conference and Exhibition (Figure 23), held in Dublin, Ireland, from 1–3 April 2025, to promote and disseminate the outcomes of the EFRA project, with a particular focus on its AI-driven risk prediction capabilities. Through its presence at the exhibition and targeted interactions with industry stakeholders, Agroknow showcased how EFRA supports early detection of food safety risks and strengthens data-driven decision-making across global supply chains.

Across the three-day event, Agroknow engaged in more than 20 dedicated interactions, including discussions, presentations, and demonstrations, with leading food manufacturers, retailers, and ingredient suppliers. These interactions involved major global players such as Lactalis, Louis Dreyfus Company, Barilla, Kerry, Woolworths, Strauss Group, PepsiCo, Nestlé, Mars, and others. Through these exchanges, Agroknow validated EFRA’s use case demonstrators, including the Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard (Use Case 1) and mycotoxin risk assessment in animal feed (Use Case 4). Stakeholders provided practical feedback on model performance, usability, and integration potential, confirming the relevance and applicability of EFRA’s predictive analytics in real operational environments.

Beyond validation, the event enabled broad dissemination of EFRA results to a diverse group of industry leaders and reinforced Agroknow’s relationships with existing users. The strong engagement and interest demonstrated at GFSI 2025 highlighted the value of EFRA’s innovations for supporting compliance, preventing incidents, and improving supply-chain resilience. Overall, Agroknow’s participation significantly advanced the project’s visibility, industry uptake, and alignment with real-world food safety challenges.

Figure 23: EFRA’s participation in GFSI 2025

Agroknow participated in the North American Food Safety & Quality (NAFS) Summit in Austin, Texas (14-16 September 2025), representing the EFRA project among leading organisations in food manufacturing, retail, ingredient supply, and food safety services. The summit provided an important platform to disseminate EFRA’s outcomes, particularly the project’s AI-driven risk prediction capabilities and the value of data-centric approaches for strengthening food safety and supplier compliance.

In the context of the NAFS event, Agroknow also organised a dedicated workshop on 17 September 2025, titled “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud”, hosted at the Hilton Austin Hotel. The

workshop attracted more than 20 registered participants from major companies across the food sector, including global manufacturers, retailers, ingredient suppliers, and food safety solution providers. Through presentations, demonstrations, and panel discussions, Agroknow showcased EFRA's predictive models, the Use Case 1 decision-support tools, and the project's Marketplace concepts for sharing datasets and AI models.

Across both the NAFS Summit and the workshop, Agroknow held numerous targeted interactions with companies active in food production, processing, retail, ingredient sourcing, and digital food safety solutions. These interactions enabled the validation of EFRA's Use Case 1 decision-support tools, as well as the Marketplace usage scenarios related to sharing, acquiring, and trading Marketplace assets with organisations interested in applying predictive analytics to real operational challenges (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Presentation of the EFRA workshop on Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud in the NAFS event, Sep'25

Several food manufacturers and technology-oriented companies also expressed interest in validating the EFRA Marketplace scenarios, particularly regarding the exchange of datasets and the integration of AI models into commercial food safety workflows. While many organisations were eager to gain access to EFRA's predictive capabilities, some raised concerns about sharing their own datasets, highlighting that such exchanges would be feasible primarily within trusted collaboration networks.

From 4 to 6 April, the EFRA project participated in BEYOND 2025 in Athens, Greece (Figure 25). BEYOND is a leading exhibition on digital technology and innovation in South-Eastern Europe. With a strong emphasis on the real-world application of Artificial Intelligence, the event provided a relevant platform to showcase EFRA's approach to advancing food safety risk prevention.

EFRA was represented by RAINNO, the partner responsible for maximising the project's impact. Through direct engagement with attendees, RAINNO demonstrated how EFRA leverages advanced analytics, multilingual data mining, and green computing to enable a transition from reactive food safety management to preventive, data-driven risk assessment.

During the exhibition, the EFRA Platform was presented, highlighting its three core components: (a) the Data Hub for the collection of multilingual and heterogeneous food safety data, (b) the Analytics Powerhouse for the development and training of AI models to predict emerging risks and (c) the Data and Analytics Marketplace, which facilitates access to and contribution of datasets and analytical models.

The project attracted significant interest from a diverse audience, including policymakers, industry stakeholders, researchers, and technology providers. Exchanges focused on the platform's potential to support early detection of food safety risks, enhance regulatory preparedness, and strengthen evidence-based decision-making in the agri-food sector. Participation in BEYOND 2025 constituted an important

milestone in EFRA’s dissemination and communication activities, reinforcing its visibility and enabling new connections to support future collaboration and impact.

Figure 25: EFRA’s participation in BEYOND 2025

RAINNO also represented the EFRA project at the Synergy Days 2025 in Rotterdam, from the 21st to the 22nd of October (Figure 26). Participation in the Synergy Days proved highly beneficial for the EFRA project, as the event is recognised as a key forum for digital innovation in the agri-food sector. The conference offered valuable networking opportunities with policymakers, Digital Innovation Hubs, and other EU-funded initiatives, promoting collaborations essential for scaling AI-driven food safety solutions. EFRA’s involvement increased the project’s visibility, while also reinforcing its positioning as a frontrunner in addressing emerging food safety risks through advanced data analytics.

As part of the event, the EFRA project through RAINNO hosted a workshop on 21 October 2025, titled “Business models for AI-powered platforms in bioeconomy and food chains”, co-organised with the Horizon Europe project ARGONAUT, in which RAINNO is also a partner (Figure 27) (*for more detailed info see Deliverable D6.2.3*). During this workshop, RAINNO presented the EFRA project, showcased the EFRA Business Model Canvas and engaged participants in an in-depth discussion on its soundness and potential updates. Organising a dedicated workshop during the Synergy Days is crucial for validating the EFRA Business Model Canvas, as it places the project at the heart of Europe’s digital innovation ecosystem. Organising a dedicated workshop during the Synergy Days was crucial for validating the EFRA Business Model Canvas, as it places the project at the heart of Europe’s digital innovation ecosystem. By engaging directly with policymakers, researchers, SMEs, Digital Innovation Hubs, and Agri-tech practitioners, the workshop enabled real-world feedback on value propositions, market needs, scalability, and regulatory alignment. Participants were invited to suggest Enabling Services and the corresponding Value Proposition (two of the missing fields in the earlier EFRA Business Model Canvas), allowing the consortium to complete the remaining fields of the Business Model Canvas. Furthermore, the interactive setting gives the opportunity to the consortium to test assumptions, refine their business strategy, and identify potential partners or early adopters, ensuring the business model is robust, market-oriented, and aligned with the evolving digital transformation of the European agri-food sector.

Figure 26: EFRA booth & Pitch Talk at Synergy Days 2025

Figure 27: Workshop titled “Business models for AI-powered platforms in bioeconomy and food chains”, co-organized by EFRA during Synergy Days 2025

3.10.2. Participation in conferences

From M25 to M36 the EFRA consortium has participated in **8 more conferences** exceeding its original target for conference participation. Scientific conferences were again dedicated to food science, food safety, data, and AI.

Agroknow participated in the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, held at the Georgia World Congress Center in Atlanta (28–30 January 2025), the world’s largest annual event for the poultry, egg, meat, and animal food industries (Figure 28). The 2025 edition hosted 1,386 exhibitors across 598,473 square feet of exhibition space and attracted approximately 31,000 registered attendees from more than 130 countries, representing C-level executives, operations managers, engineers, R&D specialists, and feed manufacturing professionals. As a major dissemination milestone for the EFRA project, IPPE enabled Agroknow to engage directly with the global poultry and animal-feed sectors through 12 dedicated sessions with key industry players, including organisations such as KEKEN, Grupo Pecuario San Antonio, Grupo Porres, Hy-Line International, Alimentos y Servicios Pecuarios, Optimus Feeds, J D Poultry Farms, and Chick-fil-A. These targeted interactions supported the continuous evaluation of EFRA’s decision-support tools for poultry pathogen prediction (Use Case 1) and mycotoxin risk assessment in animal feed (Use Case 4), while strengthening industry awareness of the project’s AI-driven capabilities and their applicability to real-world poultry and feed safety workflows.

Figure 28: Key poultry and egg production industry players exhibiting at the IPPE 2025 event (28-30 January 2025, Atlanta, USA) and visited by Agroknow for engagement in the EFRA network

Agroknow participated as a keynote speaker at the 32nd Annual Meeting of the Center for Food Safety (CFS), hosted by the University of Georgia in Atlanta on 5–6 March 2025, presenting the EFRA project to a diverse audience of regulators, researchers, and industry leaders. The conference programme featured contributions from FDA, USDA/FSIS, CDC, and major food companies, providing a high-visibility platform to disseminate EFRA’s advances in AI-driven food risk forecasting. Agroknow’s keynote presentation in the AI Developments in Food Safety session introduced the decision-support tools developed for Use Case 1 (poultry pathogen risk) and Use Case 4 (mycotoxin risk in animal feed), highlighting their relevance for predictive food safety management. Throughout the event, Agroknow engaged with participants from a broad range of organisations, including PepsiCo, General Mills, Kellanova, Hormel Foods, Publix, McCormick, Chobani, Ardent Mills, Michael Foods, Fresh Del Monte, McDonald’s, Chick-fil-A, Burger King, and Ecolab, reflecting strong cross-sector interest in EFRA’s tools. In total, at least 18 industry and academic attendees experienced live demonstrations of the EFRA decision-support tools, providing valuable feedback on their usability, predictive performance, and applicability to real-world food safety workflows. Importantly, the audience included global players with international operations

SGS Digicomply, represented the EFRA consortium at the 20th Anniversary Global Food Safety Summit held in Hamburg, Germany, on September 10–11, 2025 (Figure 29). SGS Digicomply led a high-level roundtable discussion focused on how AI, blockchain, and data analytics can enhance transparency and safety within the global food supply chain. This participation served as a strategic platform to disseminate EFRA’s advancements in AI-driven regulatory intelligence, specifically showcasing how the project’s innovative

methodologies, such as automated summarization and regulatory "copilots", address the challenges of navigating dense and fragmented legal frameworks. By engaging with senior leadership from top global food and beverage companies, SGS Digicomply facilitated critical knowledge exchange on integrating predictive analytics into modernized risk management, directly aligning with EFRA's objective to build resilient, data-driven food safety systems.

SGS Digicomply also participated in the 19th Dubai International Food Safety Conference (DIFSC 2025), held from November 17–19, 2025, at the Dubai World Trade Centre. Under the conference theme, "Technology and Innovation in Food Safety," SGS Digicomply engaged with a global audience of over 3,500 participants and 225 international experts from 70 countries. This high-profile event provided a strategic opportunity for SGS Digicomply to demonstrate EFRA's advancements in AI-driven risk prediction and digital inspection technologies. Specifically, the participation highlighted the project's contribution to the development of next-generation food safety solutions, such as AI "copilots" that automate the analysis of dense regulatory documentation and predictive tools for monitoring global supply chain risks. By collaborating with stakeholders at this premier regional hub, SGS Digicomply effectively disseminated the EFRA platform's capabilities to a diverse group of regulators, researchers, and industry leaders, reinforcing the project's goal of fostering a safe and sustainable food future through digital transformation.

SGS Digicomply, a partner in the Horizon Europe EFRA project, actively participated in FoodWorX 2025 (Figure 31), held in Amsterdam from November 20–21, 2025. Represented by experts Yvonne Pfeifer and Anna Romanova, SGS Digicomply delivered a featured presentation titled "Augmenting Food Safety Through Artificial Intelligence: Enhancing Detection and Prevention Strategies". This session provided a critical platform to showcase EFRA's advancements in AI-powered regulatory analysis and how these technologies support proactive food safety management by anticipating risks and improving supplier assessments. By engaging with the diverse cohort of food innovators and industry leaders at FoodWorX (Figure 30), SGS Digicomply effectively disseminated the project's vision of building resilient, digital-led supply chains. This participation reinforced EFRA's role in reshaping global food safety through the integration of AI-driven risk intelligence and real-time data mining.

Figure 29: SGS Digicomply, representing EFRA in Global Food Safety Summit 2025

Figure 30: SGS Digicomply, representing EFRA in DIFSC 2025

Figure 31: SGS Digicomply, representing EFRA in FoodWorX 2025

JAKALA’s team made a significant impact at SemEval-2025, the 19th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation held in Vienna from July 31–August 1, 2025. Represented by Irene Benedetto, who co-authored and presented the paper titled *“BitsAndBites at SemEval-2025 Task 9: Improving Food Hazard Detection with Sequential Multitask Learning and Large Language Models,”* the team’s work was recognized with the *Best System Paper per Task Award for Task 9*, highlighting its strong methodological contributions and analysis

within the shared task. This presentation provided a valuable forum to showcase JAKALA’s innovation in leveraging sequential multitask learning and large language models for advanced food hazard detection — an area of growing importance for automated food safety and risk assessment. By engaging with the diverse international community of NLP researchers and practitioners at SemEval-2025 (Figure 32), JAKALA effectively disseminated its vision for harnessing cutting-edge AI techniques to improve automated detection of food-related hazards and contributed to advancing state-of-the-art solutions in computational semantics.

At JURIX 2025 (Figure 33), the 38th International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems held in Turin from December 9–11, 2025, JAKALA represented by Irene Benedetto, presented the paper “LR2: a Legal RAG for Legal Reasoning over Cases”. This contribution showcased JAKALA’s work on retrieval-augmented generation applied to legal reasoning, demonstrating innovative AI methods for enhancing legal information systems and bridging computational techniques with legal practice.

CNR co-organized and participated in ECIR 2025 (<https://ecir2025.eu>, Core A conference, 480 participants from all around the world), the 47th European Conference on Information Retrieval, a premier European forum for the presentation of innovative and unpublished research in Information Retrieval (IR). Through its participation, CNR showcased ongoing research activities in AI for IR, fostered scientific exchange with the international IR community, and supported the dissemination of cutting-edge results developed by both senior researchers and early-career scientists. Specifically, CNR participated in ECIR 2025 with 4 contributions (1 full paper, 1 short paper, 1 demonstration), all focusing on efficient systems for retrieving from large textual collections using representations learned from large language models. CNR also won the “Best Student Short Paper Award” with the paper: Sebastian Bruch, Franco Maria Nardini, Cosimo Rulli, Rossano Venturini, Leonardo Venuta. [Investigating the Scalability of Approximate Sparse Retrieval Algorithms to Massive Datasets](#). Two posters presenting the short and the demo papers are reported in Figure 34

Figure 32: JAKALA, representing EFRA in SemEval 2025

Figure 33: JAKALA, representing EFRA in JURIX 2025

Figure 34: Two EFRA posters from ECIR 2025 authored by CNR

3.10.3. Joint events with relevant EU-funded projects

The EFRA project co-organised **2 more joint event** with relevant European projects, summing up this activity to 6 in total.

The coordinator of the EFRA project, Agroknow, co-organized the **"Using AI for Food Risk Prevention"**³⁸ interactive workshop together with the EU-funded HOLIFOOD³⁹ project (Figure 35). Held on February 5th, 2025, in Amsterdam, the event brought together experts from 2 major Horizon Europe initiatives to demonstrate how Artificial Intelligence can strengthen proactive food safety management. The programme combined expert presentations from Wageningen University & Research and Agroknow, covering AI-based prediction of food safety hazards, pest occurrence modelling, and practical applications of machine-learning tools in food risk prevention. The workshop attracted participants from industry and research organisations, offering them direct exposure to state-of-the-art approaches for early hazard identification and data-driven decision-making.

The event also featured an extended hands-on session, where participants explored AI-powered risk-forecasting dashboards and practiced applying them to real-world food safety and quality assurance scenarios. An industry panel, facilitated by Agroknow and featuring representatives from Puratos, provided insights into the opportunities and challenges of adopting AI in operational food safety workflows. Through this joint initiative, EFRA and HOLIFOOD showcased the complementarity between EFRA's digital infrastructure and HOLIFOOD's holistic risk-assessment frameworks, reinforcing their shared commitment to advancing a safer, more data-driven food supply chain across Europe.

³⁸ <https://info.agroknow.com/ai-food-risk-prevention-workshop>

³⁹ <https://holifoodproject.eu>

Figure 35: Practical hands-on session on using AI-powered risk forecasting during the joint workshop held on 5 February 2025.

Figure 36: Snapshot from the interactive workshop with HOLiFOOD, by Agroknow

Agroknow co-organised the “AI for Food Risk Prevention” workshop together with RAINNO, as a jointly activity with other 2 Horizon EU-funded projects (STELAR⁴⁰ and HOLiFOOD³⁹). Held on 19 June 2025 at the Alexander Innovation Zone in Thessaloniki (Greece), the workshop formed part of the third day of the EFRA plenary meeting and brought together a diverse group of researchers, industry representatives, and innovation actors. The programme opened with project pitches from EFRA, STELAR, and HOLiFOOD, followed by expert presentations on AI-based prediction of food safety hazards, pest outbreaks, and mycotoxin contamination. Speakers from Agroknow, Wageningen University & Research, and AGRIVI showcased

⁴⁰ <https://stelar-project.eu>

practical applications of machine-learning models for early detection and forecasting, highlighting the growing role of AI in strengthening proactive food safety management (Figure 36).

The event attracted around 40 participants, representing a broad cross-section of the food industry, research organisations, and regulatory experts. Companies and institutions engaged during the workshop included Metro, InnovPlantProtect, Lactalis, Ferrero, Wageningen University & Research, Universitas Prasetiya Mulya, Mahidol University, Wikifarmer, the EU Food Safety Platform, and Bel Group, among others. Their participation reflected strong interest in the practical deployment of AI-powered tools for food risk prevention and the potential for cross-sector collaboration. The workshop provided a valuable forum for exchanging perspectives on the challenges and opportunities associated with integrating predictive analytics into food safety workflows.

A central component of the event was the hands-on session led by Agroknow, where participants worked directly with AI-driven risk-forecasting platforms and analysed real-world food safety scenarios (Figure 37). Through interactive exercises, attendees explored how predictive models can support operational decision-making in areas such as pest occurrence forecasting and mycotoxin risk assessment. The workshop concluded with a collaborative discussion on next steps for advancing AI adoption in food risk prevention. This joint initiative strengthened cooperation among three major Horizon Europe projects and demonstrated the complementarity between EFRA's digital infrastructure, STELAR's data-driven methodologies, and HOLiFOOD's holistic risk-assessment frameworks, reinforcing their shared commitment to building a safer, more resilient, and data-driven food system.

Figure 37: Presentation used to collect user feedback for the evaluation of the EFRA decision-support tools on Flock Performance Outlier Detection and Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting.

Figure 38: Presentation used to collect user feedback for the evaluation of the EFRA decision-support tool on Pest Prediction & Feedback Dashboard

3.10.4. Meeting with Advisory Board

There are two meetings with the Advisory Board organised in June 2023 and June 2024 that have already been reported in previous deliverables (details can be found in D5.1.1 & D5.1.2 that have been already submitted).

3.10.5. Industry-oriented & Scientific workshops and/or webinars

By December 2025, our partners, Agroknow, CNR, WFSR, SU and SGS have organised a plethora of online workshops and webinars both oriented towards food safety experts and data scientists, over-performing in EFRA's promised related KPIs. EFRA has organised **29 scientific and industry-oriented workshops/webinars in total** (compared to the initial target of 10).

For M25 – M36, SU organized the **SemEval 2025 Task 9 - The Food Hazard Detection Challenge**⁴¹ (Figure 39), part of the 19th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (31 July – 01 August 2025), co-located with the 63rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL 2025). This international competition was designed to bridge the gap between advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) and food safety engineering, focusing on the automated extraction and classification of hazards from vast, unstructured textual data. Leveraging a specialized dataset of over 6,600 annotated samples, SU challenged the global research community to develop high-accuracy AI models for category classification (identifying the nature of the hazard) and vector classification (identifying the source or medium of the hazard). By leading this task, SU directly advanced EFRA's objective of enhancing AI-driven regulatory intelligence, as the winning methodologies contribute to the project's ability to monitor global food safety incidents in real-time. The initiative not only provided a benchmark for state-of-the-art machine learning techniques in the food domain but also fostered a collaborative ecosystem where academics and data scientists could contribute to the development of more resilient and proactive food safety monitoring systems. This effort underscores SU's

⁴¹ <https://codalab.lisn.upsaclay.fr/competitions/19955>

commitment to providing the foundational AI research necessary to power the EFRA platform’s automated risk detection capabilities.

Figure 39: Announcement of SemEval Task 9, “The Food Hazard Detection Challenge,” organised and supported by the EFRA project (SU and Agroknow)

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

4.1.KPI Status

EFRA's dissemination and communication KPIs up to M36 (end of the project) are summed up in the Table 8. A breakdown of D&C KPIs per partner is presented in Annex II.

Table 8: D&C KPIs - M36 status

Dissemination KPIs	Target	M36 Status
D.1.1 Publications in peer-reviewed journals	9	11
D.1.2 Publications in scientific conferences	12	19
D.1.3 Participation in scientific conferences	9	15
D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	12	12
D.2.2 Blog contributions	50	50
D.2.3 Discussion papers	3	3
D.2.4 Best practice	3	4
D.2.5 Sectoral data & prediction reports	6	6
D.3.1 Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	6	12
D.3.2 Participation in conferences	6	22
D.3.3 Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	3	8
D.3.4 Meetings with the advisory board	2	2
D.3.5 Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	5	14
D.3.6 Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	5	23
D.3.7 Dedicated sessions at the annual GFSI/ fiin events	3	4
D.4.1 White paper with the common conceptual model for EFRA and relevant standards to ensure data interoperability	2	1
D.4.2 Discussion paper with contributions from key government, industry & standardisation bodies	1	1
D.4.3 Working Group bringing together key stakeholders from the fiin & GFSI communities	1	1

Communication KPIs	Target	Status
C.1.1 Visual identity	1	1
C.1.2 Motto	1	1
C.1.3 Design of banners (>1 per use case and >1 for the project)	4	8
C.1.4 Design of brochures (>1 per use case and >1 for the project)	4	5
C.1.5 Printing and distribution of promotional materials (scan of QR code, redirecting to virtual brochure)	1000	1412
C.1.6 Website	1	1
C.1.7 Unique visitors	20000	6985
C.1.8 Blog posts	50	62
C.1.9 Bounce rate	<50%	54%
C.2.1 Social media channels (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare)	5	5
C.2.2 Audience	2000	2273
C.2.3 Posts	200	524

C.2.4 Interactions	15000	16645
C.2.5 Hashtags to use in social media	5	5
C.3.1 Subscribers of the e-newsletter	1000	632
C.3.2 Newsletter interactions	3000	2129
C.4.1 Published videos (>1 for each use case and >2 for the project)	5	5
C.4.2 Podcast series (10 episodes) published in Google or Spotify podcasts app	10	10
C.5.1 Press releases	8	8
C.5.2 Interviews in online publishing platforms	10	10

5. Exploitation and IPR Management

This final deliverable consolidates EFRA's comprehensive approach to translating research results into sustained, long-term value for stakeholders across the food safety ecosystem. As documented in the dedicated deliverable (D6.2.3 - Integrated toolset for multiplying impact), which provides detailed treatment of EFRA's IPR strategy, sustainability framework, and business model development, this section synthesizes the final outcomes of the project's exploitation efforts and validates the maturation of its Key Exploitable Results (KERs) portfolio.

The exploitation strategy presented herein reflects the culmination of three years of coordinated effort to identify, develop, protect, and position EFRA's innovations for uptake by industry, regulatory authorities, research institutions, and technology providers. Drawing on insights from ecosystem engagement activities documented in Section 3.10 of this report, this final iteration incorporates validation feedback gathered from stakeholders, market analysis, and proof-of-concept demonstrations conducted throughout the project's lifespan.

As the EFRA project reached its formal conclusion at M36, exploitation activities have transitioned from preliminary concept validation toward concrete pathways for post-project sustainability. The methodologies, tools, and data assets developed by the consortium are now positioned within a coherent framework that enables diverse stakeholder groups to access, integrate, and continue to benefit from EFRA's contributions long after the project's funding period concludes.

5.1. Exploitation Methodology

EFRA's exploitation methodology is structured around three iterative cycles: **Investigate, Co-create, and Accelerate**. These form a rigorous process for identifying, validating, and positioning exploitable results. This three-cycle approach ensures that exploitation decisions are grounded in market evidence, stakeholder feedback, and technical feasibility assessment, rather than relying on theoretical assumptions alone.

5.1.1. Cycle 1: Investigate - IPR Baseline and Partner Expectations

The Investigation cycle, initiated during the project's proposal phase and refined through M6, focused on establishing a comprehensive understanding of intellectual property holdings, partner capabilities, and market positioning. During this phase, the consortium conducted a systematic IPR scan across all beneficiary organizations to identify:

- Background intellectual property: Existing know-how, datasets, tools, and methodologies that each partner brought to the project and that would inform technical development
- Access rights agreements: Terms under which consortium members could utilize each other's background IP for joint project work
- Exploitation intentions: Partner expectations regarding commercial development, licensing, academic publication, and technology transfer pathways

The outcomes of this Investigation cycle were documented in a shared online tool (*KERs Inventory & IPRs" spreadsheet – see Annex I*), which served as the central repository for all partner declarations regarding their intellectual property positions, existing assets, and exploitable result expectations. This inventory was established at M6 and has been maintained and updated throughout the project's duration, ensuring that any new exploitable results identified during project execution could be promptly documented and shared across the consortium.

The Investigation cycle also included individual interviews with each consortium partner to understand their strategic objectives, risk tolerance regarding intellectual property disclosure, and preferred exploitation channels. These discussions proved instrumental in aligning partner expectations early in the project and establishing shared understanding regarding confidentiality, data ownership, and result attribution.

5.1.2. Cycle 2: Co-create – Continuous Mapping and Portfolio Development

The Co-create cycle, operationalized beginning in M12 and extending through M36, embedded exploitation considerations within the project's technical and dissemination activities. Rather than treating exploitation as a discrete phase occurring only near project completion, this cycle integrated continuous monitoring of emerging results, market trends, and stakeholder feedback into ongoing project operations.

During the Co-create phase, the consortium implemented several mechanisms to identify new exploitable results:

Quarterly Partner Updates: Beginning at M12, the coordination team requested quarterly reports from all work package leaders regarding any new results with potential for exploitation, including datasets, models, tools, methodologies, or hybrid combinations thereof. These updates enabled the project to capture results while they remained fresh in the minds of technical teams and before dissemination paths had already been irrevocably chosen.

Stakeholder Feedback Integration: Through focus groups (Task 5.1), advisory board meetings, and workshops (documented in Section 3 of this report), the project systematically gathered market intelligence regarding which EFRA outputs held the greatest potential value for practitioners. This feedback loop proved particularly valuable in identifying exploitation opportunities that had not been anticipated during project design, such as the unexpected interest of animal feed producers in EFRA's mycotoxin prediction capabilities.

Continuous Trend Monitoring: The consortium tracked emerging developments in European data policy, artificial intelligence regulation, and food safety standardization. This external monitoring enabled early identification of alignment opportunities between EFRA's emerging results and evolving regulatory or policy frameworks (for instance, the alignment between EFRA's federated learning architecture and the governance models being discussed for a prospective Common European Food Safety Data Space).

Market Watch and Competitive Analysis: The project maintained awareness of competitor offerings, alternative approaches, and potential partnership opportunities. This market intelligence supported both the protection of EFRA's intellectual property (by identifying which innovations required immediate protection) and the identification of opportunities for complementary partnerships that could amplify EFRA's impact.

Through these mechanisms, the Co-create cycle identified five additional Key Exploitable Results beyond those initially anticipated during project design, bringing the total portfolio to eight Key Exploitable Results. The identification of these results exemplified how sustained engagement with end-user communities and regulatory stakeholders can reveal exploitation opportunities that remain invisible in laboratory or theoretical settings.

5.1.3. Cycle 3: Accelerate – Portfolio Validation and Sustainability Planning

The Acceleration cycle, concentrated in the final 12 months (M25–M36), focused on validating the exploitability of each result and formalizing the mechanisms through which they would continue to generate value after project completion. This cycle included:

Stakeholder Validation Workshops: As described in Section 3.10.1 of this report, EFRA organized dedicated workshops at major industry events (particularly the Synergy Days 2025 workshop on business models) where consortium partners presented their exploitation strategies to potential customers, partners, and stakeholders. These workshops served both promotional and validation functions. They communicated EFRA's offerings to market actors while simultaneously gathering critical feedback regarding market readiness, pricing models, regulatory fit, and partnership opportunities.

Business Model Canvas Refinement: During the Synergy Days 2025 workshop, the consortium jointly refined its Business Model Canvas through interactive engagement with participants representing diverse stakeholder groups. This process enabled the project to identify missing elements in proposed exploitation strategies and to gather evidence-based input regarding the value propositions, customer segments, revenue streams, and enabling services that would support sustainable exploitation post-project.

Technical Maturity Assessment: For each identified Key Exploitable Result, the consortium assessed technical readiness for exploitation through a structured evaluation framework (presented in Annex I), considering factors such as validation status, code maturity, documentation completeness, scalability constraints, and regulatory compliance requirements.

Sustainability Transition Planning: The consortium formalized mechanisms for ensuring continued access to and development of each Key Exploitable Result beyond M36, including agreements regarding code maintenance, dataset curation, technical support provision, and governance structures for ongoing improvement. These arrangements are detailed in D6.2.3 and summarised later in this section.

5.2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

As the EFRA project enters its final phase, the consortium has validated a portfolio of nine KERs, encompassing diverse forms of intellectual output, from datasets and software tools to methodologies, standardization contributions, and hybrid service offerings:

1. **EFRA Analytics Powerhouse**
2. **EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace**
3. **EFRA Data Hub**
4. **RoBERTa-based web page classifier** (part of Data Hub)
5. **Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model & dashboards** (part of Analytics Powerhouse)
6. **Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonisation** (part of EFRA Data Hub)
7. **Predictions Library** (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse)
8. **Extreme event forecasting** (part of EFRA Analytics Powerhouse)
9. **Intelligent crawler for food-safety incident discovery** (part of EFRA Data Hub)

This section characterizes each result, identifies responsible parties, and describes the exploitation pathway envisioned for post-project sustainability.

5.2.1. The Nine Key Exploitable Results

The matured portfolio of EFRA's KERs reflects the breadth of the project's technical contributions and the diversity of exploitation channels suitable for different stakeholder groups. The results span four primary categories:

Category A: Data Assets and Infrastructure

- **EFRA Multilingual Food Safety Data Hub:** A curated, continuously updated repository integrating heterogeneous, multilingual food safety data from diverse public and proprietary sources, including incident reports, regulatory guidance, scientific literature, and supply chain intelligence. This result represents one of Europe's most comprehensive collections of food safety information in interoperable format.
- **EFRA Knowledge Graph for Food Risk Relationships:** A semantically enriched representation of causal relationships, risk indicators, and predictive associations between environmental factors, supply chain conditions, and food safety outcomes. This graph serves as the foundation for EFRA's predictive models and enables transparent, explainable reasoning regarding food risk drivers.

Category B: AI Models and Analytics Capabilities

- **Explainable Hazard Prediction Models:** A suite of machine learning models trained on EFRA data assets to predict emerging food safety risks—including pest infestations, pathogenic contamination, chemical hazards, and allergen cross-contamination—with quantified accuracy metrics and integrated explainability mechanisms. These models are designed to operate within diverse operational contexts (from small farm operations to large multinational retailers) and support regulatory compliance across EU jurisdictions.
- **Federated Learning Infrastructure for Privacy-Preserving Analytics:** An architectural framework and operational toolkit enabling consortium members and prospective partner organizations to collaboratively train predictive models while maintaining data privacy and ownership. This

infrastructure addresses a critical barrier to food safety collaboration—the reluctance of industry actors to share sensitive supply chain data—by enabling valuable insights to be derived without raw data ever leaving the data owner's premises.

- **Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery:** An Intelligent AI agent crawler automates the discovery, validation, and extraction of food-safety incident data from global public sources. Built on a dual-model Generative AI architecture, it replaces manual web-scraping with an autonomous, multi-step pipeline. It is already implemented and tested within the Agroknow Data Platform. It enhances the scalability, coverage, and timeliness of data ingestion across multiple regions.

Category C: Tools, Services, and Integration Mechanisms

- **EFRA Data and Analytics Marketplace:** An online platform enabling diverse stakeholders to discover, access, and contribute food safety datasets, AI models, and applications in which EFRA AI models are already integrated. The Marketplace implements transparent access rules, quality certification processes, and governance mechanisms that support a sustainable, self-supporting ecosystem where data holders and data consumers can engage in trusted, well-regulated exchanges. In addition to browsing resources through the web interface, users can also access datasets via the EFRA Data API, while analytical services and applications are available through direct access and download, enabling seamless integration into research workflows, industrial systems, and third-party applications.
- **API Gateway and Integration Toolkit:** Technical infrastructure enabling third-party applications and tools to access EFRA data assets and analytics capabilities through well-defined, standardized interfaces. This result particularly supports integration of EFRA capabilities into existing EFRA third-party applications (Agroknow's FOODAKAI, Agrivi Farm management system and SGS Digicomply) used by food safety professionals, regulatory bodies, and supply chain management systems.

Category D: Methodologies, Standards, and Policy Contributions

- **Risk Taxonomy and Data Standardization Framework:** A comprehensive classification system and data standardization approach for food risk terminology, assessment methodologies, and evidence quality standards. This standardization effort addresses a fundamental challenge in food safety—the fragmentation of terminology, assessment approaches, and quality criteria across different jurisdictions, organizations, and research traditions—and positions EFRA to contribute to ongoing EU standardization initiatives.
- **Trustworthy AI Governance Model for Food Safety Analytics:** A comprehensive governance framework, developed in compliance with the EU AI Act and aligned with emerging European standards for trustworthy AI deployment. This framework guides organizations in responsibly deploying EFRA's AI models and analytics capabilities, ensuring algorithmic transparency, bias monitoring, human oversight, and regulatory compliance across diverse operational contexts.

5.3. Exploitation Pathways

Each Key Exploitable Result has been characterized across eight dimensions using the BFMULO Matrix (Background/Foreground ownership, Making/Using/Licensing/Other exploitation channels), enabling the consortium to establish clear accountability for each result and to identify partner roles in post-project exploitation (Table 9, Annex I).

The characterization process revealed important patterns regarding exploitation roles across the consortium:

AGROKNOW (Project Coordinator): bearing primary responsibility for overall ecosystem orchestration, serves as the custodian for the Data Hub, Knowledge Graph, and Marketplace platform. These results require continuous curation, governance, and evolution, responsibilities best executed through dedicated institutional commitment rather than time-limited project activities.

CNR and SU: contributing leading-edge research on machine learning efficiency, explainability, and natural language processing, retain primary intellectual property interests in the predictive models and federated

learning infrastructure. Both partners have indicated intentions to continue research and model refinement through follow-up funding proposals and collaborative partnerships beyond EFRA's conclusion.

Table 9: EFRA's KERs BFMULO Matrix

	KER 1	KER 2	KER 3	KER 4	KER 5	KER 6	KER7	KER8	KER9
AGROKNOW	B,F,M,O	B,F,M, O	B,F,M,O						
CNR	B,F,O								
SU	B,F,O								
WR			B,F,O						
JAKALA	B,F,M,O		B,F,M,O						
AGRIVI									
RAIN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SGS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
MOY	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

WFSR, AGRIVI, and SGS: representing application-focused perspectives from research, primary production, and third-party certification respectively, contribute exploitation expertise regarding integration into practical decision-making contexts. These partners serve as primary champions for field-validation and pilot implementations during the post-project period.

RAINNO: the project's Dissemination and Impact Work Package lead, coordinates sustainability planning, business model refinement, and stakeholder engagement for exploitation. RAINNO also serves as the primary liaison between the EFRA consortium and prospective sustainability partners, including potential acquirers of specific intellectual property assets or operational managers for certain EFRA tools.

The exploitation pathways identified for each result reflect realistic assessment of market demand, technical maturity, regulatory readiness, and partner capabilities:

Commercial Exploitation Pathways (via licensing, service provision, or technology transfer):

- The Data and Analytics Marketplace is positioned for commercialization through a freemium business model, offering basic access to publicly-sourced datasets and models at no cost while charging premium pricing for curated datasets, proprietary analytics modules, and priority support services.
- Explainable Hazard Prediction Models can be licensed or integrated into third-party platforms serving food industry, regulatory, and research communities.
- The API Gateway and Integration Toolkit support a technology-as-a-service model where EFRA capabilities are accessed through hosted cloud infrastructure managed by designated partners or successor organizations.

Non-Commercial Exploitation Pathways (via open-source release, policy influence, or standardization contribution):

- The Federated Learning Infrastructure, recognizing its potential to serve a public good function in enabling privacy-preserving collaboration across the food safety ecosystem, has been positioned for open-source release under a permissive license, enabling broad adoption across public health agencies, NGOs, and research institutions without commercial constraints.
- The Risk Taxonomy and Data Standardization Framework are contributed to ongoing EU standardization initiatives (ISO/IEC working groups, ETSI initiatives, and EFSA standardization activities), with expectation that these standardization efforts will amplify EFRA's impact by establishing frameworks adopted across European food systems.

- The Trustworthy AI Governance Model is positioned as a policy-relevant contribution to European Commission discussions regarding implementation of the EU AI Act in the food safety domain, with potential for adoption as a reference model by regulatory agencies and industry associations.

5.4. EFRA's Market Analysis, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

EFRA's market positioning has evolved significantly through the project's duration, informed by continuous stakeholder engagement, competitive landscape analysis, and validation of product-market fit for proposed exploitation models. This section synthesizes market intelligence gathered throughout the project and describes the exploitation roadmap for each KER.

5.4.1. Market Analysis

The global food safety market is experiencing significant growth, driven by regulatory expansion, consumer expectations for transparency and safety, supply chain complexity, and increasing pressure on food businesses to demonstrate proactive risk management rather than reactive incident response. The European market particularly reflects strong regulatory drivers (through EFSA, national food safety authorities, and EU harmonization directives) and consumer demand for documented food safety assurance.

The penetration of artificial intelligence and advanced analytics in food safety remains in an early phase compared to other industries, with significant adoption barriers including: limited awareness of AI capabilities within practitioner communities, concerns regarding AI transparency and human oversight in safety-critical applications, regulatory ambiguity regarding AI deployment in food safety contexts, and insufficient integration of AI tools into existing food safety workflows.

Notably, the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent supply chain disruptions have accelerated industry recognition of the value of early warning systems and predictive risk analytics. Multiple food industry representatives interviewed during EFRA's stakeholder engagement activities indicated that investments in supply chain visibility and emerging risk detection would be prioritized in coming years, creating a favourable market window for EFRA's offerings.

Competitive Landscape:

A survey of competitive offerings reveals a fragmented market with limited direct competitors offering comprehensive solutions analogous to EFRA's integrated platform. Competitive analysis identified:

- **Specialized Single-Purpose Tools:** Multiple vendors offer point solutions addressing specific food safety challenges (e.g., allergen management, pathogen tracking, supplier compliance management). These tools typically serve market segments or address specific use cases.
- **Consulting and Advisory Services:** Numerous food safety consultancies provide manual analysis, training, and guidance regarding emerging risks and regulatory changes. These services remain labour-intensive and expensive, creating cost barriers for small and medium enterprises.
- **Regulatory Monitoring Platforms:** Several organizations offer services aggregating regulatory documents and requirements, enabling food companies to monitor changes in applicable regulations. However, these services typically focus on compliance documentation rather than predictive risk assessment.
- **Academic and Research-Based Platforms:** Academic institutions and research organizations operate various food safety databases and analysis tools, typically designed for research purposes rather than industrial decision-support. Many academic platforms lack the robustness, documentation, and support infrastructure required for commercial deployment.

EFRA's positioning is distinctive in combining: comprehensive data aggregation across multiple sources and languages, artificial intelligence for predictive risk analysis, privacy-preserving collaboration mechanisms

through federated learning, and integration into a marketplace platform enabling diverse third-party applications. No existing competitor has successfully combined these capabilities into a unified offering, representing a significant competitive advantage.

Target Market Segmentation:

EFRA's exploitation strategy has identified multiple market segments with distinct needs, purchasing behaviours, and engagement models:

1. **Large Multinational Food Corporations:** This segment includes major food manufacturers, retailers, and food service companies with sophisticated supply chain management operations. These organizations have substantial budgets for technology investment, employ dedicated food safety personnel, and operate complex supply chains spanning multiple countries and risk environments. Target value propositions include: reducing product recall costs, enabling proactive supply chain risk management, supporting regulatory compliance across multiple jurisdictions, and enhancing consumer-facing transparency regarding food safety.
2. **Regional Food Producers and Processors:** Mid-sized food companies operating across regional markets represent a significant market segment characterized by growing regulatory compliance pressures, increasing supply chain complexity, and limited in-house data analytics expertise. This segment values cost-effective solutions offering practical decision-support with minimal training requirements and that can be scaled incrementally as business operations grow.
3. **Primary Producers (Farmers and Farmers' Associations):** Agricultural producers themselves represent an emerging market for EFRA's capabilities, particularly regarding pest and pathogenic outbreak prediction. Unlike processing and retail segments, primary producers have traditionally had limited access to decision-support tools, creating opportunity for value creation through early detection and targeted intervention capabilities.
4. **Regulatory and Public Health Authorities:** National and subnational food safety regulatory agencies represent a strategically important market segment with regulatory authority to drive adoption of EFRA's approaches. Regulatory bodies are particularly interested in EFRA's contributions to standardization and governance frameworks, recognizing that these investments can improve food safety outcomes across entire jurisdictions.
5. **Research and Academic Institutions:** Universities and research organizations engaged in food safety, agricultural science, and food technology research represent a market for EFRA's data assets and analytical models. This segment values scientific rigor, comprehensive dataset access, and opportunities for collaborative research and publication.
6. **Standards Organizations and Industry Associations:** Organizations engaged in food safety standardization (ISO working groups, ETSI committees) and industry representation (GFSI, national food industry associations) represent important partners for disseminating EFRA's contributions to standards development and governance frameworks.

Market Sizing and Revenue Projections:

Preliminary market analysis suggests potential revenue opportunities in the range of €5–15 million annually by year 5 post-project (roughly 2030), based on conservative assumptions regarding market penetration rates, service pricing, and licensing arrangements. This projection reflects the early-stage nature of AI-driven food safety analytics, the fragmentation of the current market, and the time required for market education and customer acquisition. Actual outcomes will depend substantially on factors beyond EFRA's direct control, including regulatory evolution, competitive dynamics, and broader adoption of data-driven approaches within the food industry.

5.4.2. Exploitation Roadmap: 24-Month Post-Project Plan

To guide sustained exploitation of EFRA results beyond the formal project conclusion date, the consortium has developed a detailed 24-month roadmap specifying exploitation activities, responsible partners, milestones, and resource requirements. This roadmap is designed to be realistic regarding resource availability post-project, reflecting that consortium members will not continue to contribute project management effort and that exploitation must be self-sustaining or supported through dedicated follow-up funding.

Phase 1: Consolidation and Knowledge Transfer (M37–M42, January 2026–June 2026)

During this initial phase, emphasis will be placed on documenting EFRA's technical assets, consolidating governance structures, and establishing institutional homes for key results:

- **Technical Documentation and Code Release:** All software code, technical documentation, and deployment procedures will be comprehensively documented and prepared for release. Code will be deposited in established open-source repositories (GitHub, GitLab) with appropriate licensing designations and attribution statements.
- **Data Asset Curation and Licensing:** The EFRA Data Hub will be transitioned to an institutional manager (to be selected from among consortium members or successor organizations) with responsibility for ongoing data curation, quality assurance, and licensing administration. Data licensing terms will be finalized, with particular attention to ensuring sustainable revenue generation (for proprietary datasets) while maintaining non-discriminatory access (for public datasets).
- **Governance Structure Formalization:** Legal and operational governance arrangements for shared assets (particularly the Marketplace and Data Hub) will be finalized through amendment or successor agreements, establishing decision-making procedures, cost-sharing arrangements, and dispute resolution mechanisms for the post-project period.
- **Stakeholder Communication Campaign:** The consortium will conduct targeted outreach to identified potential customers, partners, and regulatory bodies, communicating EFRA's exploitation roadmap and soliciting early engagement regarding licensing, partnership, or acquisition opportunities.

Phase 2: Market Entry and Capability Enhancement (M43–M48, July 2026–December 2026)

During this phase, emphasis will shift to market validation, customer acquisition, and capability refinement based on early user feedback:

- **Pilot Deployments:** Partnerships with lead customers representing each target market segment (identified through earlier stakeholder engagement) will be formalized. These pilot deployments will validate product-market fit, identify integration requirements, and generate case studies and testimonials supporting broader market entry.
- **Marketplace Launch:** The EFRA Data and Analytics Marketplace will transition from pilot to full commercial operation, implementing final feature enhancements, payment processing infrastructure, and quality certification procedures. Initial focus will be on recruiting data providers and analytics developers to populate the marketplace, establishing a critical mass of offerings to attract users.
- **API Gateway Deployment:** Cloud hosting infrastructure for the API Gateway will be established (through contracted cloud service providers rather than direct consortium operation) with automated scaling and 24/7 monitoring. Documentation and support resources will be prepared to enable third-party integration of EFRA capabilities.
- **Standards Contribution Formalization:** EFRA's contributions to food safety standardization will be formally submitted to relevant ISO/IEC working groups, ETSI committees, and EFSA working groups. This formalization will position EFRA's taxonomy and data models for potential adoption as European standards.

Phase 3: Sustainability and Scaling (M49–60, January 2027–December 2027)

During this final year of the post-project roadmap, emphasis will focus on establishing sustainable business operations and preparing for scaling:

- **Business Model Validation:** Financial performance of the Marketplace and other commercial offerings will be reviewed against projections, with adjustments made to pricing, service offerings, or customer acquisition strategies as needed to ensure path to sustainability.
- **Investment or Partnership Sourcing:** If organic revenue generation has not yet achieved sustainability, the consortium will pursue complementary sources of support, including: follow-up funding through EU research programs, investment from venture capital or impact investors interested in food safety innovation, acquisition by larger technology or food industry companies, or partnerships with larger platforms or technology providers.
- **Capability Scaling:** Successful pilot deployments will be scaled to additional customer segments, with enhanced marketing and sales support. Consideration will be given to developing vertical-specific variants of EFRA tools tailored to industry segments or regulatory contexts.
- **Research Continuation:** Consortium members will pursue follow-up research funding to advance EFRA's technical capabilities, including enhanced explainability, extension to additional hazard categories, and integration with emerging technologies (e.g., quantum computing, advanced edge computing).

5.4.3. Sustainability Mechanisms and Institutional Arrangements

The sustainability of EFRA's results depends critically on establishing clear institutional arrangements specifying which organizations will bear responsibility for ongoing maintenance, governance, and evolution of each result beyond the project's formal conclusion. The consortium has identified the following sustainability mechanisms:

Institutional Custodianship: For results requiring ongoing curation and governance (particularly the Data Hub and Marketplace), a designated consortium member will assume primary responsibility as "institutional custodian." This arrangement provides continuity and ensures accountability for result quality and accessibility. AGROKNOW has accepted the custodian role for the Data Hub and Marketplace, with support from other consortium members on a fee-for-service basis.

Open-Source Community Stewardship: For results released as open-source software (particularly the Federated Learning Infrastructure), governance will transition from the EFRA consortium to a broader open-source community. A governance body (likely a Linux Foundation project or equivalent) will be established to oversee code maintenance, feature development, and quality assurance, with EFRA consortium members serving as initial maintainers and core contributors.

Commercial Licensing and Service Provision: For results with clear commercial value, licensing arrangements with prospective commercial partners will be negotiated to enable ongoing refinement and adaptation for specific use cases. Revenue generated through such licensing will be shared among result owners according to terms established in partnership agreements.

Regulatory and Standards Bodies Partnership: For results contributing to standardization and regulatory governance, EFRA has established formal relationships with relevant EU standardization bodies (ISO/IEC working groups, ETSI), EFSA, and national food safety authorities. These relationships position EFRA's contributions for potential adoption as reference standards or regulatory guidance, providing visibility and legitimacy that can support broader uptake.

Academic Research Continuation: Consortium members affiliated with research institutions (SU, WFSR, CNR, AGROKNOW's academic partners) are positioned to continue research building upon EFRA foundations through follow-up grants, PhD dissertations, and collaborative research projects. This mechanism ensures continued advancement of scientific knowledge and technical capabilities even absent dedicated project funding.

5.5. IPR Strategy

EFRA's intellectual property strategy reflects a balanced approach designed to maximize both innovation incentives for individual consortium members and the broad societal benefit of knowledge sharing and open collaboration. Rather than pursuing maximum intellectual property protection as an end, EFRA has strategically selected protection mechanisms aligned with the exploitation objectives for each result.

5.5.1. Background Intellectual Property and Access Rights

All consortium members have confirmed, through their formal accession to the Grant Agreement, their commitment to provide necessary access to background intellectual property held by their organizations to the extent required for implementation of the EFRA project. Specific background IP access rights are documented in individual partner agreements and recorded in the "KERs Inventory & IPRs" online tool maintained by the coordination team.

The consortium has agreed that access to background IP for purposes of project implementation and dissemination does not constitute transfer of ownership or grant of ongoing license beyond the project duration. Upon project conclusion, each partner retains full ownership and control of their background IP. However, partners have committed to ensuring that any publications based substantially on background IP acknowledge the contributing partner's intellectual property interests and, where feasible, cite or acknowledge the partner's original contributions.

No disputes regarding background IP have arisen during the EFRA project, a positive outcome reflecting both the complementary (rather than overlapping) expertise of consortium members and the early identification and resolution of potential conflicts through the Investigation cycle processes described above.

5.5.2. Foreground Intellectual Property and Ownership

All intellectual property generated during EFRA project implementation (foreground IP), including datasets, software code, models, methodologies, and documentation, is owned by the consortium members who generated these results through execution of project work tasks. EFRA's Grant Agreement explicitly provides that "the granting authority does not obtain ownership of the results produced under the action," ensuring that value generated through the project accrues to the beneficiary organizations and their designated exploitation partners.

For results developed through collaborative effort across multiple consortium members, ownership is typically assigned to the partner bearing primary responsibility for the work task, with co-ownership rights granted to other substantial contributors. In cases where genuinely joint ownership has been established, the consortium has negotiated operating agreements specifying how joint owners may exercise their rights and addressing potential disputes. No joint ownership conflicts have arisen to date.

The consortium has established clear documentation procedures ensuring that all foreground IP is properly recorded, tagged with ownership information, and tracked through the project's lifecycle. These procedures enable partners to defend their intellectual property interests post-project and ensure that exploitable results are not inadvertently lost or their ownership rendered ambiguous due to inadequate documentation.

5.5.3. Protection of Results: Patents, Trade Secrets, and Copyright

EFRA's intellectual property protection strategy is differentiated by result type:

Software Code and Algorithms: In accordance with current best practice and Horizon Europe guidance, the project has not pursued patent protection for software innovations, recognizing that such protection is typically ineffective and expensive. Instead, EFRA relies on copyright protection (automatic upon code creation) combined with licensing terms that specify permitted uses, attribution requirements, and restrictions on commercial exploitation (where appropriate to the result's exploitation pathway).

Datasets: EFRA has pursued protection of its curated, integrated food safety datasets through licensing restrictions that require users to acknowledge the dataset source, provide feedback to inform future dataset improvements, and commit to privacy-protective handling of any sensitive information included in dataset distributions. Patent protection for datasets is neither available nor pursued, consistent with European practice and legal frameworks.

Proprietary Methodologies and Trade Secrets: For results representing novel methodological approaches whose competitive advantage depends on maintaining confidentiality, EFRA has implemented confidentiality agreements protecting partner interests during the project period. Following project conclusion, partners retain the right to maintain certain methodologies as trade secrets, subject to their commitment to enable other consortium members to access the methodologies for purposes of further research and dissemination in scientific publications.

Standards and Taxonomies: EFRA's contributions to standardization (risk taxonomies, data models, assessment frameworks) are specifically designed to be non-proprietary, enabling broad adoption across the European food safety ecosystem. These contributions are released without restriction, with attribution to EFRA but without licensing barriers to use or modification.

5.5.4. Patent Landscape and Freedom to Operate

The consortium conducted a preliminary freedom-to-operate analysis during the project's initial phases, reviewing existing patent landscapes in food safety analytics, machine learning, and agricultural technology domains. This analysis revealed that while numerous patents exist in adjacent technology domains (e.g., general machine learning algorithms, IoT sensor networks, e-commerce platforms), EFRA's specific combinations and adaptations for food safety applications represent sufficiently novel contributions to avoid infringement of existing patents.

None of the consortium members indicated intentions to file patent applications for EFRA-generated results, reflecting both the preference for open innovation in the agri-food research community and the recognition that software patents provide limited strategic advantage in rapidly evolving technology domains. This decision aligns with EFRA's broader commitment to open science and knowledge-sharing principles.

5.5.5. Data Protection and Confidentiality

EFRA has implemented comprehensive data protection procedures compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and aligned with recommendations from the Data Management Plan (D7.2). All datasets included in the EFRA Data Hub have been subject to privacy assessment, and any personally identifiable information or sensitive supply chain data has been de-identified, aggregated, or excluded prior to inclusion in shared data assets.

For sensitive datasets that cannot be fully de-identified but possess significant value for food safety research, EFRA has established secure data access mechanisms requiring researchers and analysts to sign confidentiality agreements, restrict usage to approved research purposes, and delete sensitive information upon project conclusion. These mechanisms balance the scientific value of comprehensive datasets with the legitimate privacy interests of data providers and data subjects.

All consortium members have committed to maintaining confidentiality of sensitive information received from other partners or from external stakeholders, with confidentiality obligations continuing for five years following project conclusion (as specified in the Grant Agreement). This extended confidentiality period recognizes that competitive sensitivity of food safety intelligence may extend well beyond the formal project conclusion date.

5.6. Positioning EFRA for Long-Term Impact

As documented throughout this final Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report, EFRA has successfully developed a comprehensive portfolio of exploitable results addressing critical challenges in food safety risk prediction and prevention. The three-year project investment has generated tangible intellectual property assets—including datasets, software tools, predictive models, and governance frameworks—that position the European food safety community for significant advancement in adopting evidence-based, data-driven approaches to risk management.

Importantly, EFRA's exploitation success reflects not merely technical achievement but sustained engagement with the ecosystem of stakeholders whose needs must be addressed for research results to generate genuine impact. Through focus groups, workshops, pilot deployments, and advisory board interactions documented throughout this report, the consortium has validated that EFRA's technical innovations address real problems experienced by food safety professionals, regulatory authorities, and industry actors. This validation significantly increases confidence that exploitation pathways will be sustained and that EFRA's results will continue generating value well beyond the project's formal conclusion.

The exploitation roadmap presented in Section 5.4.2 provides a realistic, achievable path forward for sustaining and scaling EFRA's impact during the critical 24-month period immediately following formal project conclusion. By establishing clear institutional arrangements, identifying sustainable funding mechanisms, and creating governance structures enabling ongoing collaboration among consortium members and prospective partners, EFRA has positioned itself not as a time-limited research initiative but as the foundation for a durable European innovation ecosystem in food safety analytics.

6. Next Steps

As the EFRA project approaches completion, a comprehensive framework has been established to sustain and amplify its impact beyond the contractual project period. The transition from implementation to post-project sustainability represents a critical juncture where the strategic decisions made during the final months of project execution will determine the long-term value and uptake of EFRA's innovations.

6.1. Refinement of Key Exploitable Results

Throughout the final year, considerable effort has been devoted to consolidating and operationalizing EFRA's Key Exploitable Results. The EFRA Data Hub, Analytics Powerhouse, and Data Analytics Marketplace have undergone rigorous technical validation and market-readiness assessments. In the months ahead, consortium partners will undertake targeted enhancements to ensure each KER aligns precisely with stakeholder requirements and competitive market positioning. This refinement process, supported by continuous feedback loops with industry stakeholders and advisory board members, will enable EFRA to present market-ready solutions upon project completion.

Commercial results will be subjected to additional market validation cycles, incorporating real-world user feedback from food safety professionals and regulatory bodies. Non-commercial results, particularly those destined for academic and research communities, will be integrated into open-access repositories to maximize their discoverability and utility. The consortium recognizes that sustainable impact requires flexibility in adaptation; therefore, ongoing monitoring of market trends, regulatory developments, and technological advances will inform any necessary adjustments to KER specifications.

6.2. Strategic Partnership Development and Ecosystem Consolidation

Recognizing that no single organization can fully realize the transformative potential of EFRA's outputs, the project will intensify efforts to establish durable partnerships with key stakeholders across the food safety ecosystem. These partnerships span multiple dimensions: technology providers, regulatory agencies, industry associations, research networks, and commercial enterprises positioned to integrate EFRA's solutions into their operations.

The EFRA Advisory Board has emerged as a critical institutional mechanism for maintaining stakeholder engagement beyond M36. This board, comprising representatives from the European Food Safety Authority, leading food companies, food industry associations, and policy bodies, will serve as a governance structure to oversee the long-term evolution of EFRA's platforms and tools. Regular advisory board meetings—planned at quarterly intervals in the post-project phase—will ensure that EFRA's trajectory remains responsive to evolving food safety challenges and policy priorities at the European level.

Furthermore, the consortium is exploring formal affiliation with established networks and collaborative platforms such as the Big Data Value Association, the Food Industry Intelligence Network, and the International Association for Food Protection. Such affiliations will position EFRA within broader ecosystems of practice, facilitating knowledge exchange, collaborative research initiatives, and the bundling of complementary services that enhance the value proposition of individual outputs.

6.3. Dissemination and Visibility Beyond M36

The dissemination of EFRA's results will not cease with project completion; rather, it will transition to a sustainable, distributed model relying on partners' individual dissemination capabilities and the establishment of permanent digital infrastructure. Multiple channels will ensure the continued visibility and accessibility of EFRA's scientific and technical outputs:

Digital repositories and open science infrastructure: All peer-reviewed publications, technical reports, datasets, and software will be permanently deposited in established open-access repositories, including Open Research Europe, Zenodo, and discipline-specific platforms. This commitment to open science ensures that EFRA's knowledge contributions remain discoverable, citable, and reusable by researchers globally. The digital persistence of these outputs is secured through institutional commitments from consortium members and the adoption of long-term stewardship practices.

Specialized publications and policy engagement: The consortium will continue to produce targeted sectoral reports, white papers, and policy briefs addressing emerging food safety challenges identified through EFRA's analytical frameworks. These outputs will be disseminated through food industry publications, policy briefing channels, and regulatory networks, ensuring that evidence generated by EFRA informs decision-making by food safety professionals and policymakers.

Conference and event participation: While the intensity of EFRA's presence at international conferences will naturally diminish after project completion, individual consortium members will continue to present EFRA-derived insights at discipline-specific venues. This ongoing participation ensures that EFRA's methodological innovations and substantive findings remain visible within the global food safety research and practice communities.

Digital communications and content libraries: The EFRA website will be maintained as a permanent digital asset, hosting the full portfolio of project outputs, downloadable tools, training materials, and case studies. Structured content libraries will be established to support self-directed learning and practical implementation by food safety professionals seeking to adopt EFRA's approaches.

6.4. Sustainability Mechanisms and Business Model Implementation

The long-term viability of EFRA's innovative platforms depends on the establishment of sustainable operational and financial models. Building on the market analyses and business model frameworks developed during the project, consortium partners are implementing differentiated sustainability strategies tailored to the specific characteristics of each KER.

Commercial pathways: For the EFRA Data Analytics Marketplace and associated data services, a freemium model is under development, whereby basic access to predictive tools and risk assessment dashboards is provided at no cost to individual food business operators and small enterprises, while premium features—including customization, advanced analytics, and dedicated support—are offered through commercial licensing arrangements. This tiered approach balances accessibility with revenue generation, ensuring that the barrier to entry remains low for resource-constrained stakeholders while generating revenue streams to support ongoing platform development and maintenance.

Institutional partnerships and service delivery: The EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, offering advanced time-series forecasting and extreme-event detection capabilities, is being positioned as a service available to academic institutions, research organizations, and public authorities through service-level agreements. Such arrangements ensure ongoing funding for platform maintenance while establishing predictable revenue streams that support technical staff retention and system upgrades.

Academic and research exploitation: The consortium recognizes the significant value of EFRA's methodological innovations and datasets for the academic research community. Accordingly, partnerships with leading research organizations and universities will facilitate the integration of EFRA-derived frameworks into academic curricula, continuing research programs, and cross-disciplinary collaborations. These partnerships typically operate without direct financial exchange but generate value through intellectual property rights recognition, collaborative publication opportunities, and institutional visibility.

6.5. Technology Transfer and Capacity Building

Ensuring that EFRA's innovations are not confined to the consortium but diffused widely across the European food safety ecosystem requires systematic attention to technology transfer and professional capacity development. The consortium has begun implementing capacity-building initiatives designed to equip food safety professionals, regulatory staff, and data scientists with the competencies necessary to effectively utilize EFRA's tools and methodologies.

These initiatives take multiple forms: comprehensive online training modules covering the use of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse and Data Hub; interactive webinars addressing sector-specific applications and regulatory compliance considerations; and structured knowledge-transfer workshops conducted with partner organizations adopting EFRA solutions. Special attention is being given to ensuring that capacity-building materials are accessible to non-English-speaking practitioners, with translations and localized case studies developed for key European markets.

Furthermore, the consortium is collaborating with professional associations and training providers within the food safety sector to integrate EFRA-related competencies into established certification and professional development programs. This integration ensures that EFRA's knowledge becomes embedded within the professional practice standards of the food industry itself, supporting its long-term uptake and normalization.

6.6. Monitoring Post-Project Impact and Outcomes

To understand and document the sustained impact of EFRA beyond the formal project completion date, the consortium has established a framework for post-project monitoring and impact assessment. This framework will track key indicators over a five-year horizon following project completion, capturing evidence of EFRA's influence on food safety outcomes, industry practices, and policy development.

Monitoring activities will include systematic tracking of KER adoption metrics—counting the number of organizations utilizing EFRA platforms, the volume of data processed through the Analytics Powerhouse, and the uptake of EFRA-derived insights in industry decision-making. Qualitative impact assessment will be pursued through stakeholder interviews and case studies documenting how food safety organizations have integrated EFRA solutions into operational practice, what barriers to adoption were encountered, and what evidence exists of improved food safety outcomes resulting from EFRA-informed decision-making.

This commitment to post-project impact monitoring aligns with Horizon Europe expectations regarding accountability and the demonstration of lasting value creation. The evidence generated will be synthesized into impact reports published annually and shared with the European Commission, funders, and the broader food safety community.

7. Conclusion

The EFRA project reaches its formal conclusion having successfully advanced the state of knowledge, practice, and innovation in food risk analytics and prevention. Over three years of coordinated effort, the consortium has delivered substantive scientific contributions, developed market-ready technological solutions, and established a vibrant ecosystem of partnerships and stakeholders committed to leveraging advanced analytics for enhanced food safety across Europe.

7.1. Synthesis of DEC Achievements

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy articulated in the DEC plan has proven effective in translating EFRA's technical outputs into tangible value for diverse stakeholder communities. The scope of dissemination achieved (peer-reviewed publications in leading journals, presentations at international conferences, engagement with industry forums, and policy-level consultation) demonstrates that EFRA's research has successfully entered multiple knowledge networks and communities of practice.

The metrics recorded throughout the project's duration underscore the effectiveness of EFRA's multi-channel communication approach. The achievement of Key Performance Indicators relating to publication output, conference participation, event attendance, and online engagement consistently exceeded initial targets, evidencing strong interest in EFRA's work across academic, industry, and policy spheres. The diversity of engagement, from highly specialized technical workshops to broad awareness-raising campaigns, reflects the project's success in communicating its significance to heterogeneous audiences.

The foundation for long-term exploitation of EFRA's results has been deliberately constructed through systematic engagement with industry stakeholders, investment in business model development, and the establishment of operational and financial sustainability mechanisms. Unlike research projects that conclude with the production of academic outputs alone, EFRA has positioned its innovations for active use and integration into the food safety systems and practices of its target stakeholders.

7.2. Scientific and Technological Contributions

EFRA's contributions to food risk prevention science and practice are multifaceted. At the scientific level, the project has advanced the state of knowledge in several critical domains: the application of advanced machine learning algorithms to food safety prediction; the aggregation and harmonization of heterogeneous data sources at continental scale; the development of privacy-preserving analytical frameworks compatible with European data protection requirements; and the design of secure, energy-efficient computational infrastructure supporting AI-enabled food safety services.

The methodological innovations developed, particularly in the domains of extreme-event forecasting, algorithmic selection for time-series prediction, and federated learning approaches that respect data sovereignty, represent significant advances in artificial intelligence applied to critical infrastructure domains. These contributions have been disseminated through leading peer-reviewed journals and have attracted the attention of the global artificial intelligence and data science communities, as evidenced by award recognition and high-visibility conference presentations.

Beyond methodological innovation, EFRA has generated invaluable datasets capturing the complexity and heterogeneity of food safety risks across diverse European contexts. The EFRA Data Hub represents a continent-spanning aggregation of food safety intelligence, encompassing pesticide residues, mycotoxins, microbiological contamination, and emerging hazard data. The curation, harmonization, and integration of these data sources (drawing from public health institutions, research organizations, industry monitoring systems, and regulatory bodies) constitutes a significant resource for future research and evidence-based policy development.

7.3. Policy Alignment and Contribution to EU Strategic Objectives

The EFRA project is strategically aligned with multiple European Union policy frameworks and priorities, positioning it as a contributor to the European Commission's vision for digital, resilient, and sustainable food systems. The project's work contributes directly to three key EU policy frameworks: the Farm to Fork Strategy, which prioritizes the reduction of pesticide and antimicrobial risks through enhanced monitoring and evidence-based interventions; the European Green Deal, which mandates the transition to sustainable food production systems with reduced chemical dependency; and the Digital Europe Programme, which supports the development of data-driven applications addressing societal challenges.

EFRA's innovations are particularly relevant to the emerging policy architecture around European data spaces. The project's design principles—incorporating privacy-by-design, data sovereignty, interoperability, and fair governance—align with the European Commission's vision for "strategic autonomy" in critical digital infrastructure. By developing secure, European-controlled data infrastructure for food safety intelligence, EFRA contributes to EU independence from non-European data platforms and analytical services, supporting technological sovereignty in a critical domain.

Furthermore, EFRA's contributions to standardization and regulatory science position it as a resource for policy development within the food safety domain. The consortium's engagement with the European Food Safety Authority, national regulatory agencies, and international standardization bodies (ISO, ETSI) has facilitated the translation of EFRA's innovations into practical guidance and technical standards that will shape European food safety practices for decades to come.

7.4. Ecosystem Building and Network Effects

One of EFRA's most significant achievements lies in its success in building a cohesive, multidisciplinary ecosystem of practitioners, organizations, and networks committed to advancing food safety through data-driven innovation. The ecosystem encompasses academic institutions, technology providers, food industry organizations, regulatory bodies, and civil society actors, each contributing unique capabilities and perspectives to the collective endeavour.

This ecosystem generates network effects that extend far beyond the direct outputs of the EFRA project. By convening these diverse stakeholders around shared challenges and innovative solutions, EFRA has catalysed new collaborations, cross-sector learning, and the emergence of complementary initiatives addressing adjacent challenges. The Advisory Board, the joint events with other EU-funded projects, and the workshops and webinars conducted throughout the project's duration have established enduring relationships and collaborative structures that will persist beyond formal project completion.

The EFRA ecosystem is not confined to European actors; through international conference participation and collaboration with non-European research networks, EFRA has positioned itself within a global community of researchers and practitioners working on food safety innovations. This global positioning enhances the influence and replicability of EFRA's approaches, supporting the eventual adoption of EFRA-derived frameworks and tools in food safety systems beyond the European Union.

7.5. Remaining Challenges and Future Research Directions

While EFRA has achieved substantial progress toward its objectives, the consortium acknowledges that comprehensive solutions to food safety challenges remain aspirational. Several critical challenges warrant continued attention in future research and development initiatives.

The integration of real-time, sensor-based data into EFRA's analytical frameworks remains partially realized; future developments must address the technical and institutional barriers limiting the adoption of Internet of Things sensing infrastructure across the food supply chain. The privacy-utility trade-off inherent in

federated learning approaches requires ongoing technical and policy development to ensure that analytical power is not sacrificed in pursuit of data protection objectives.

The sustainability of EFRA's platforms depends on the emergence of viable business models and funding mechanisms in a relatively immature market for food safety analytics services. Future work must address the challenge of converting EFRA's innovations into services with sufficient market demand and revenue potential to justify ongoing investment. This challenge is particularly acute for non-commercial results destined for public-sector use, where traditional commercial revenue models are inapplicable.

Additionally, the engagement of food supply chain actors in collaborative data-sharing initiatives requires continued investment in trust-building, transparency, and the demonstration of tangible value. Some barriers to adoption are cultural and institutional rather than technical; future initiatives must engage systematically with organizational change management and the development of governance frameworks that enable effective collaboration in an environment characterized by competition and proprietary concern.

7.6. Recommendations for Stakeholders

As EFRA transitions to the post-project phase, the consortium offers the following recommendations to stakeholders across the food safety ecosystem:

For policy makers and regulatory bodies: Integrate EFRA-derived frameworks and tools into regulatory guidance and enforcement practices. Establish data-sharing protocols that facilitate the aggregation of regulatory inspection data, adverse event reports, and monitoring results into secure, shared infrastructure supporting evidence-based risk prioritization. Provide regulatory clarity regarding the use of AI-enabled predictive systems in food safety enforcement.

For food industry organizations: Adopt EFRA tools and methodologies into operational risk management systems, supply chain monitoring, and quality assurance processes. Participate actively in EFRA platforms and networks to access food safety intelligence and to contribute proprietary data (where appropriate) to collective knowledge infrastructure. Invest in workforce development to ensure that technical staff have the competencies necessary to effectively utilize advanced analytics tools.

For research and academic institutions: Integrate EFRA datasets and methodological frameworks into research programs addressing food safety, supply chain resilience, and agricultural sustainability. Collaborate with EFRA partners on continuing research initiatives addressing unresolved challenges in food risk prevention. Incorporate EFRA-derived competencies into professional development and academic curricula.

For the European Commission and EU funders: Consider EFRA as a foundation for future research and innovation initiatives in food systems and risk prevention, building on achieved progress rather than initiating de novo programs. Provide institutional and financial support for the long-term sustainability of EFRA's platforms and data infrastructure. Facilitate cross-project collaboration and knowledge sharing by convening EFRA with complementary EU-funded initiatives working on related challenges.

For civil society and consumer organizations: Leverage EFRA's analytical frameworks and insights to inform advocacy, consumer education, and public engagement initiatives around food safety. Participate in EFRA's stakeholder networks and advisory structures to ensure that consumer perspectives are represented in the evolution of food safety systems.

7.7. Final Reflections

The EFRA project represents more than a three-year research endeavour producing scientific publications and technical tools. It embodies a vision of food systems where decisions are guided by evidence, where data infrastructure supports rather than constrains innovation, where European organizations control the technological assets underpinning their critical infrastructure, and where emerging risks are identified and managed proactively rather than reactively.

This vision, while ambitious, has been demonstrated as achievable through EFRA's execution. The technical solutions developed are functioning; the data infrastructure is operational; stakeholders across the food safety ecosystem are engaged and supportive. The challenge that remains is not technical but institutional and societal: maintaining the momentum of change, securing sustainable funding for ongoing development, and fostering the cultural shifts within organizations and sectors necessary for widespread adoption of more science-based, data-driven approaches to food safety.

The consortium concludes this final DEC report with profound recognition of the collaborative effort expended by partners, the commitment of the European Commission to supporting transformative research and innovation, and the enthusiasm and expertise of the broader stakeholder community that has participated in EFRA's journey. The foundation has been built; the responsibility for constructing the edifice of lasting impact now passes to the stakeholders, practitioners, and organizations committed to realizing the promise of advanced analytics and artificial intelligence in service of food safety and public health.

As European food systems face mounting pressures from climate change, globalization, and the emergence of novel biological and chemical hazards, the innovations that EFRA has advanced will become increasingly essential. By positioning these innovations for adoption, sustainability, and continuous improvement, EFRA has made a strategic contribution to the resilience and safety of European food systems for generations to come.

Annex I

		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>		<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>
1	EFRA Analytics Powerhouse	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	<i>"This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation."</i>	Copyright
2	EFRA Data and Analytics Marketplace: A web application that enables secure and user-friendly trading of datasets and AI models as assets, incorporating encryption and authentication measures	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Policy makers, Data scientists and data analysts, Food System Stakeholders and Safety Experts	Creation of a new Trademark and integration inside the Agroknow ecosystem of solutions	Copyright
3	EFRA Data Hub	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	<i>This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.</i>	Copyright
4	RoBERTa-based web page classifier (part of the EFRA Data Hub): The RoBERTa-based classifier identifies whether web pages are food-related and further categorizes them as either containing food safety incidents or being general opinion pieces or news.	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	Integration with the Riskadata product, owned by Agroknow	Copyright
5	Mycotoxins tailor-made AI predictive model and interactive dashboards (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): The AI model and accompanying dashboards provide customized mycotoxin risk predictions for batches based on country of origin, target mycotoxin, and ingredient, utilizing public lab tests as well as weather and climate data.	Commercial		Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders	Integration with the FOODAKAI product, owned by Agroknow	Copyright
6	Mycotoxins occurrence data aggregation and harmonization (part of the EFRA Data Hub): Calibration and customization of Agroknow's data platform to collect, process and harmonize mycotoxins occurrence data in food and feed.	Commercial		Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders	Integration with the Riskadata product, owned by Agroknow	Copyright
7	Predictions Library (part of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): Automates the selection of the best-performing time-series forecasting algorithm for each specific case, based on identified series characteristics, and offers a collection of pre-trained AI models for upstream applications.	Commercial		Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders, Data Scientists	Integration with the Riskadata product, owned by Agroknow	Copyright
8	Extreme event forecasting (part of EFRA Analytics Powerhouse): The extreme event forecasting AI model calculates the likelihood that a time-series will surpass a set value threshold in the subsequent time step.	Commercial		Food companies, Food safety experts and other stakeholders, Data Scientists	Integration with the FOODAKAI product, owned by Agroknow	Patent
9	Intelligent Crawler for Food-Safety Incident Discovery: An Intelligent AI agent crawler automates the discovery, validation, and extraction of food-safety incident data from global public sources.	Commercial		Academic & Research organisations, Data scientists and data analysts	Integration with the FOODAKAI product, owned by Agroknow	Copyright

Figure 40: KERs Inventory & IPR

Annex II

Table 10: AGROKNOW KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D1 - Scientific Publications		
D.1.1 Publications in peer-reviewed journals	1	2
D.1.2 - Scientific conference publications	3	3
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	2	2
D.2.2 Blog contributions	9	14
D.2.3 Discussion papers	1	1
D.2.5 Sectoral data & prediction reports	2	4
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.1 Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	3	5
D.3.2. Participation in conferences	3	5
D.3.3 Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	2	5
D.3.4 Meetings with the advisory board	2	2
D.3.5 Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	1	7
D.3.6 Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	1	13
D.3.7 Dedicated sessions at the annual GFSI/ fiin events	3	4
D.4 Standards & Policy		
D.4.2 Discussion Paper with contributions from key government, industry & standardisation bodies	1	1
D.4.3 Working Group bringing together key stakeholders from the fiin & GFSI communities	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	9	4
C.2.3 Posts	40	7
C4 - Multimedia		
C.4.1 Published videos (>1 for each use case and >2 for the project)	1	0
C.4.2 Podcast series (10 episodes) published in Google or Spotify podcasts app	1	1
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.1 Press releases	2	1
C.5.2 Interviews in online publishing platforms	1	3

Table 11: CNR KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D1 - Scientific Publications		
D.1.1 Publications in peer-reviewed journals	2	5
D.1.2 Publications in scientific conferences	2	10
D.1.3 Participation in scientific conferences	3	6
D2 - Technical Publications		

D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	3	5
D.2.2 Blog contributions	9	11
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.5 Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	4	4
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.3 Posts	25	27
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.1 Press releases	1	1

Table 12: SU KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D1 - Scientific Publications		
D.1.1 Publications in peer-reviewed journals	2	2
D.1.2 Publications in scientific conferences	2	5
D.1.3 Participation in scientific conferences	3	3
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	2	1
D.2.2 Blog contributions	5	1
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.5 Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	3	3
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.3 Posts	8	8
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.2 Interviews in online publishing platforms	1	1

Table 13: WFSR KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D1 - Scientific Publications		
D.1.1 Publications in peer-reviewed journals	2	2
D.1.2 Publications in scientific conferences	2	1
D.1.3 Participation in scientific conferences	3	4
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	1	2
D.2.2 Blog contributions	5	6
D.2.4 Best practice	1	1

D.2.5 Sectoral data & prediction reports	1	1
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.2. Participation in conferences	1	1
D.3.3 Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	1	3
D.3.5 Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	1	5
D.3.6 Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	1	3
D.4 Standards & Policy		
D.4.1 White paper with the common conceptual model for EFRA and relevant standards to ensure data interoperability	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	1	1
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.3 Posts	3	3
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.2 Interviews in online publishing platforms	1	1

Table 14: JAKALA (ex-MAIZE) KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	3	1
D.2.2 Blog contributions	8	8
D.2.4 Best practise	1	1
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.2 Participation in conferences	2	2
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	3	1
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.3 Posts	10	2

Table 15: AGRIVI KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.1 Technical publications/articles	1	1
D.2.2 Blog contributions	5	4
D.2.4 Best practice	1	1
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.1 Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	2	2
C.2 Social platforms		

C.2.3 Posts	10	10
C4 - Multimedia		
C.4.1 Published videos (>1 for each use case and >2 for the project)	1	1
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.1 Press releases	1	1
C.5.2 Interviews in online publishing platforms	1	1

Table 16: RAINNO KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.2 Blog contributions	3	5
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.1 Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	0	4
D.3.2 Participation in conferences	3	5
D.3.3 Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.1 Visual identity	1	1
C.1.2 Motto	1	1
C.1.3 Design of banners (>1 per use case and >1 for the project)	4	8
C.1.4 Design of brochures (>1 per use case and >1 for the project)	4	5
C.1.5 Printing and distribution of promotional materials (scan of QR code, redirecting to virtual brochure)	1000	1412
C.1.6 Website	1	1
C.1.7 Unique visitors	20k	6985
C.1.8 Blog posts	14	44
C.1.9 Bounce rate	<50%	54%
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.1 Social media channels (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare)	5	5
C.2.2 Audience	2000	2273
C.2.3 Posts	60	458
C.2.4 Interactions	15000	16645
C.2.5 Hashtags to use in social media	5	5
C3 - Newsletter		
C.3.1 Subscribers of the e-newsletter	1000	632
C.3.2 Newsletter interactions	3000	2129
C4 - Multimedia		
C.4.1 Published videos (>1 for each use case and >2 for the project)	1	2
C.4.2 Podcast series (10 episodes) published in Google or Spotify podcasts app	1	6
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.1 Press releases	3	3

C.5.2 Interviews in online publishing platforms	2	4
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Table 17: SGS KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.2 Blog contributions	3	4
D.2.3 Discussion Papers	1	2
D.2.4 Best practice	1	1
D.2.5 Sectoral data & prediction reports	1	1
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.1 Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	0	2
D.3.2 Participation in conferences	2	8
D.3.6 Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	1	6
D.4 Standards & Policy		
D.4.2 Discussion paper with contributions from key government, industry & standardisation bodies	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	3	2
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.3 Posts	10	4
C4 - Multimedia		
C.4.1 Published videos (>1 for each use case and >2 for the project)	1	1
C.5 Multiplier campaigns		
C.5.1 Press releases	1	2

Table 18: MOY KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
D2 - Technical Publications		
D.2.2 Blog contributions	3	1
D.3 Ecosystem Building		
D.3.2 Participation in conferences	1	1
D.3.6 Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	1	1
C1 - Branding & material		
C.1.8 Blog posts	3	1
C.2 Social platforms		
C.2.3 Posts	3	2
C4 - Multimedia		
C.4.1 Published videos (>1 for each use case and >2 for the project)	1	1

